

ExtremeXP

Experiment Driven and user Experience Oriented Analytics for
Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions

**D4.2: Human-in-the-Loop services – User intents,
profiles, feedback**

Project Acronym/Title	Experiment Driven and user Experience Oriented Analytics for Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions
Grant Agreement No.:	101093164
Call	HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01
Project duration	36 months 01 January 2023 – 31 December 2025
Deliverable title	Human-in-the-Loop services – User intents, profiles, feedback
Deliverable reference	D4.2
Version	1.0
WP	4
Delivery Date	30/09/2025
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Deliverable lead	UPC
Authors	Besim Bilalli, Petar Jovanovic, Sergi Nadal, Adrià Aumatell, Gerard Pons, Marc Maynou, Alexis Lacapelle
Reviewers	Stavros Maroulis, Albert Calvo, Konstantinos Tsopelas
Abstract	This deliverable documents the final status of the ExtremeXP's Human-in-the-Loop services, responsible for anticipating and capturing user intents, generation of complex analytics workflows and obtaining end users feedback on the provided experiments, by means of gamification. More precisely, this document describes three main software artifacts of the Human-in-the-Loop services: (1) Anticipation and capturing of user intents, (2) Intent to complex workflow generator, and (3) Gamification-based user feedback module. The deliverable includes links to the software code and libraries that implement the aforementioned modules. It also documents their implementation and provides usage Information.
Keywords	Intent, workflows, user-in-the-loop, user feedback, user profile

Dissemination Level	
PU	Public, fully open
Type	
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

Version History

Version	Date	Owner	Author(s)	Changes to previous version
0.1	2024-10-02	UPC	Petar Jovanovic	ToC prepared with some annotations about the future content.
0.2	2024-12-15	UPC	Petar Jovanovic	Added contents from interim report and assigning responsibility for all the sections.
0.3	2025-06-25	UPC	Petar Jovanovic	Provided introductory section and background for better understanding the deliverable.
0.4	2025-07-29	UPC	Sergi Nadal, Adrià Aumatell, Marc Maynou	Added new content regarding the capturing and automated mapping of user intents to complex analytics workflows (T4.3).
0.5	2025-08-25	UPC	Besim Bilalli, Gerard Pons	Added new content regarding the user profile and context prediction for intent anticipation (T4.4) .
0.6	2025-09-10	UPC	Petar Jovanovic	Edited (introduction, background) + Added new content (Human-in-the-loop services – Architecture and UI).
0.7	2025-09-24	I4D	Alexis Lacapelle	Added new content regarding the gamified simulations for user feedback collection and analysis.
0.8	2025-09-26	ARC	Stavros Maroulis	Review
		I2CAT	Albert Calvo	Review
		ARC	Konstantinos Tsopelas	Review
0.9	2025-09-29	All	Besim Bilalli, Petar Jovanovic, Sergi Nadal, Adrià Aumatell, Gerard Pons, Marc Maynou, Alexis Lacapelle	Address reviewers' comments + proofreading, corrections on comments
1.0	2025-09-30	UPC	Petar Jovanovic, George Papastefanatos, Athanasios Mantes	Final version for submission

Table of content

Version History	3
Table of content	4
List of Figures	7
List of Tables	9
List of Acronyms	10
Executive Summary	12
1. Introduction	13
1.1 Objectives	13
1.2 Structure	13
2. Human-in-the-Loop services in ExtremeXP - Background	14
2.1 Main concepts	14
2.2 Semantic-based backbone (Knowledge Graph)	15
3. Capturing and automated mapping of user intents to complex analytics workflows (T4.3) ...	16
3.1 General Overview	16
3.2 Ontology design	17
3.2.1 TBOX	18
3.3 I2WG pipeline	19
3.3.1 Dataset annotator.....	20
3.3.2 Abstract planner	21
3.3.3 Logical planner.....	22
3.3.4 Workflow translator.....	24
3.4 Evaluation	25
3.4.1 Use case validation	25
3.4.2 Time performance	27
3.4.2.1 Ontology generation	28
3.4.2.2 Datasets	29
3.4.2.3 Results.....	30
3.4.3 Quality assessment	31
4. User profile and context prediction for intent anticipation (T4.4)	33
4.1 Automatic Capturing and Classification of Analytical Intents	33
4.1.1 Categorization of Analytical Intents.....	34
4.1.2 On the Use of LLMs for Automatic Intent Classification	34
4.1.3 Validation Data Collection	35
4.1.4 Experimental Evaluation.....	36
4.2 Automatic Capturing and Classification of Constraints	37

4.2.1	Knowledge Graph Extension	37
4.2.2	Constraints Taxonomy	38
4.2.3	Integration with Intent Capturing	39
4.3	Mapping Intents and Constraints to Knowledge Graph Concepts	39
4.3.1	Motivation and Problem Statement	39
4.3.2	Overview	39
4.3.3	Proposed method: ED with KG-enhanced LLMs	40
4.3.3.1	Problem Formulation	41
4.3.3.2	Method	41
4.3.4	Experimental evaluation	43
4.3.4.1	Settings and Datasets	43
4.3.4.2	Results	44
4.3.4.3	KG Expressivity Impact	46
4.3.4.4	Error Analysis	47
4.4	Intent Recommendation via Knowledge Graph Embeddings	48
4.4.1	Data Instantiation	48
4.4.2	Workflow Annotation	48
4.4.3	Recommending/Anticipating User Intents	49
4.4.3.1	Basic Approach	49
4.4.3.2	Exploiting the Graph's Structure	50
4.4.3.3	Knowledge Graph Embeddings	50
4.4.3.4	Link Prediction	51
4.4.4	Experimental Evaluation	51
4.4.4.1	Methodology	52
4.4.4.2	Experiment	55
4.4.4.3	Results	55
4.4.5	Domain Expert Validation	59
4.5	Maintenance and Updates of Knowledge Graph Embeddings	61
4.5.1	Overview	61
4.5.2	Methodology	62
4.5.3	Experimental evaluation	63
4.5.3.1	Experimental setting	64
4.5.3.2	Initialization Effect on Incremental Learning Approaches	66
4.5.3.3	Number of Training Epochs	66
4.5.3.4	Number of New Entities	69
4.5.3.5	Different KGE Models	69
5.	<i>Gamified simulations for user feedback collection and analysis (T4.5)</i>	72

6. Human-in-the-Loop services for ExtremeXP (Architecture and UI demonstration) 76

7. Conclusion..... 82

References..... 83

List of Figures

Figure 1: Knowledge graph backbone for HITL services	15
Figure 2: End-to-end pipeline to generate complex analytics workflows from intents	17
Figure 3: I2WG TBOX concepts	18
Figure 4: Dataset annotator overview	20
Figure 5: Fragment of data set graph produced for titanic dataset	21
Figure 6: Abstract planner overview	21
Figure 7: Abstract plan for decision tree	22
Figure 8: Logical planner overview	22
Figure 9: Logical plan for titanic dataset classification	23
Figure 10: Fragment workflow graph generated for titanic dataset classification.....	24
Figure 11: Workflow translator overview	24
Figure 12: KNIME workflow for titanic dataset classification	25
Figure 13: Workflow produced for cybersecurity use case	25
Figure 14: Cybersecurity use case output example	26
Figure 15: Workflow produced for manufacturing use case	26
Figure 16: Manufacturing use case output example	27
Figure 17: Livelock example	28
Figure 18: Example of generated ontology with depth level = 2 and CPI = 1. Each node represents a different implementation and each edge an input-output shape requirement between them.....	29
Figure 19: Generated I2WG workflow to solve binary classification for Penguins dataset	31
Figure 20: Naïve workflow created for Penguins dataset.....	31
Figure 21: Intent Categorization	34
Figure 22: A systematic method for the validation of analytical intent text classifiers.....	35
Figure 23: Example applied on the ExtremeXP KG backbone.....	38
Figure 24: Taxonomy of AutoML constraints.....	39
Figure 25: Overview of the two steps of our approach	40
Figure 26: Overview of the steps for simplifying candidate subgraphs into a DAG for pruning	41
Figure 27: Example of the three different configurations of the LCA’s direct successors.....	42
Figure 28: Class representation of the entity Barcelona in DBpedia (left) and YAGO (right) KGs.....	46
Figure 29: Instantiation of a template constraint.....	49
Figure 30: Example of an SPARQL query over the KG.....	50
Figure 31: Simplified 2D visualization of the intuition behind the different translational embedding models.....	50
Figure 32: Overview of classes and properties relevant for the anticipation task	51

Figure 33: Hits@3 score grouped by Embedding Dimension (left) and dependence of Hits@3 score with Embedding Dimension for different models, with fixed LR, 0.001, and NPP 20 (right).	56
Figure 34: Hits@3 score grouped by NPP (top-left) and influence of the NPP parameter on different models.....	57
Figure 35: Effect of the learning rate on the evaluation (left) and on the training loss (right) for a fixed model (ComplEx, Embedding Dimension=32, NPP=20).....	57
Figure 36: Boxplot summary of the Hits@3 score grouped by Model	58
Figure 37: Conceptual representation of the potential disruption (represented with a shading area) of existing embeddings when the embedding of a new entity with which they appear in a triple is initialized in a distant (left) or close (right) position from the optimal (left).....	61
Figure 38: Illustration of the overall process for updating KGE with new information.....	62
Figure 39: Example of the ontology information for the triple [J. Phoenix, actedIn, Joker]	63
Figure 40: Hits@3, Ω_{new} and Ω_{base} for datasets with different update sizes, when using random, ontology and model initializations.....	68
Figure 41: Effect of training with reduced number of epochs for different initialization strategies with the ENTITY-100 dataset	71
Figure 42: Overview of HITL services in the ExtremeXP framework.....	76
Figure 43: End user's intent provisioning (left: Expert user intent selection; right: Novice user textual intent expression)	76
Figure 44: Intent definition	77
Figure 45: Intent constraint recommendation	77
Figure 46: Logical planner (results of the Abstract planner)	78
Figure 47: Abstract workflow (SVM).....	78
Figure 48: Workflow planner (results of the Logical planner)	79
Figure 49: Logical plan (SVM, z-score, mean imputation)	79
Figure 50: Final workflows for export and use in Experimentation Engine.....	80
Figure 51: XXP (eXtremeXP) file format of the produced workflow	81

List of Tables

Table 1: Execution time in seconds, generated workflows, and speed for Titanic dataset	30
Table 2: Execution time in seconds, generated workflows, and speed for UC2 dataset	30
Table 3: Performance results of a minimal workflow versus the I2WG workflow per dataset.....	32
Table 4: Preliminary Intent Classification Evaluation	35
Table 5: Search queries for the three validation datasets. “-” means that no textual statements were found for the corresponding class (intent).	36
Table 6: Number of retrieved (Ret), discarded in the preprocessing (D-Pre) or in the verification (D-Ver) files	36
Table 7: Accuracy on expanded validation sets	37
Table 8: Precision and recall for each intent class with GPT-4	37
Table 9: Overview of ten considered datasets’ statistics	43
Table 10: Results for the inKB micro F1-score for the ED experiments with ten datasets.....	45
Table 11: Metric comparisons from YAGO and DBpedia KGs [23]	46
Table 12: Percentage of disambiguated entities in which the pruning algorithm reached a final single entity within the specified number of iterations.....	47
Table 13: Error types for the ACE2004 and KORE datasets, using YAGO as the KG	47
Table 14: Example of features extracted from the datasets, depending on the target variable	48
Table 15: Summary of the number of triples present in each source	55
Table 16: Hyperparameter optimization final configuration and results	59
Table 17: Recommendation output for the domain expert validation of the LP model. For each dataset, the top three intents, metrics and constraints are provided. The errors identified by the expert are highlighted in bold	60
Table 18: Number of triples in each snapshot for the different datasets. Snapshot 0 being the base/initial KG.....	64
Table 19: Effect of different initialization strategies on various incremental learning approaches for ENTITY-100.....	66
Table 20: Relative percentage difference between Ontology and Random initialization with various KGE models. Large or >100% values occur when the baseline (Random) is very small; negative values indicate performance degradation.....	69

List of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ABOX	Assertional Box
AD	Anomaly Detection
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Association Rule Mining
AUC	Area under the curve
AutoML	Automated Machine Learning
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
CA	Correlation Analysis
CAW	Complex Analytic Workflow
CBOX	Controlled Vocabularies Box
CI	Causal Inference
CL	Clustering
CS	Classification
CSV	Comma-separated values
CV-QA	Culturally-diverse multilingual Visual Question Answering benchmark
DA	Data Abstraction (component of ExtremeXP framework)
DAG	Directed-acyclic graph
DL	Domain Language
DMOP	Data Mining OPTimization Ontology
DP	Data Profiling
ED	Entity Disambiguation
EL	Entity Linking
ETL	Extract-Transform-Load
FC	Forecasting
FPM	Frequent pattern mining
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
HITL	Human-in-the-Loop
I2WG	Intent-to-Workflow Generator
KG	Knowledge Graph

KGE	Knowledge Graph Embeddings
KG-QA	Knowledge Graph Question Answering
KNN	k-nearest neighbours algorithm
LCA	Lowest Common Ancestor
LLM	Large Language Model
LOOCV	Leave-one-out cross-validation
LP	Link Prediction
LSTM	Long short-term memory
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
ML	Machine Learning
MRR	Mean Reciprocal Rank
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NN	Neural network
OWL	Web Ontology Language
OWL DL	Sublanguage of Web Ontology Language based on Description Logics
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RE	Regression
RoBERTa	Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SPARQL	SPARQL (Semantic) Protocol and RDF Query Language
SVM	Support vector machine
TBOX	Terminological Box
UI	User Interface
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
WP	Work package
XGBoost	eXtreme Gradient Boosting classification algorithm
XXP	eXtremeXP (experimentation engine file extension)

Executive Summary

This deliverable documents the final status of the ExtremeXP's Human-in-the-Loop services, responsible for anticipating and capturing user intents, generation of complex analytics workflows and obtaining end users feedback on the provided experiments, by means of gamification. More precisely, this document describes three main software artifacts of the Human-in-the-Loop services: (1) Anticipation and capturing of user intents, (2) Intent to complex workflow generator, and (3) Gamification-based user feedback module. The deliverable includes links to the software code and libraries that implement the aforementioned modules. It also documents their evaluations and provides usage information.

1. Introduction

The ExtremeXP project introduces a paradigm shift in data analytics through its experimentation-driven, user-centered framework for producing accurate, precise, fit-for-purpose, and trustworthy data-driven insights.

Central to this vision is the inclusion of the end user—not merely as a passive recipient of analytical outcomes, but as an active participant in shaping the analytics process. This is achieved through a human-in-the-loop approach that starts from end users' perspective of the analytical process (i.e., intent) and continuously learns from user interactions, preferences, and feedback to adapt and optimize complex analytics workflows over time.

One of the main objectives of WP4 is to enhance user access to the ExtremeXP framework and learn from previous user interactions to provide a smoother experience for users inside the system. The deliverable 4.2 reports on the progress and final status of the Human in the loop (HITL) services within the ExtremeXP framework which are being finalized in month 33 of the project. These services are results of the work done in the Tasks T4.3, T4.4, and T4.5 of WP4.

1.1 Objectives

The main goal of the HITL services is to enable end users' interaction with the ExtremeXP framework, specifically focusing on users without high technical skills and with the aim of providing a smoother user experience within the framework. In particular, the HITL services include:

- (i) *Capturing user intents (T4.3)*, i.e., allowing end users via an intuitive graphical user interface to express their intents (e.g., detect if there is an anomaly in the manufacturing process and the type – electric or mechanic), as well as constraints and preferences (e.g., accuracy over 80% and minimize the size of the workflow)
- (ii) *Mapping user intents into complex analytics workflows (T4.3)*, i.e., following the previously captured user intent with constraints and preferences, automatically create possible variations of complete complex analytics workflows that allow the analysis to satisfy user's analytical needs.
- (iii) *Creating user profiles (T4.4)*, i.e., based on users' activity and interaction with HITL services, characterize and create representative user profiles that can allow recommendations and simulations of user activity.
- (iv) *Anticipating user intents (T4.4)*, i.e., using user's profiles and gathered metadata about users' interactions in the system, allows to anticipate user intents and recommend potentially interesting analysis for the user.
- (v) *User feedback collection and analysis via gamification (T4.5)*, i.e., employ gamification methods to gather user feedback about the previously proposed analysis.

1.2 Structure

D4.2 is organized as follows: Section 2 briefly presents the background necessary for comprehending the HITL services, introducing the main concepts and the semantic-based metadata backbone for governing and automating the processes within HITL services. Section 3 presents the results of Task 4.3 on capturing and automated mapping of user intents to complex analytics workflows. Section 4 describes the results of Task 4.4 on context prediction for intent anticipation and creation of user profiles. Section 5 presents the results of Task 4.5 on user feedback collection and analysis via gamified simulations. Section 6 presents the integration of HITL services within the ExtremeXP framework and

the related user interface. Section 7 concludes the deliverable, by summarizing the key outputs of our work in WP4 with regard to HITL services.

2. Human-in-the-Loop services in ExtremeXP - Background

2.1 Main concepts

In this section, we give an overview of the main concepts of the HITL services of the ExtremeXP framework. Some terminology has been already reported through other deliverables (e.g., D2.1)

Complex Analytics Workflow (CAW). It is an abstraction over different types of data-driven analytics workflows that includes (possibly combinations of): (i) machine learning (ML) workflows possibly materialized through ML tools like KNime¹; (ii) job scheduling and task automation workflows, which can be materialized in Activeeon's ProActive tool; (iii) custom data analysis scripts²; (iv) extract-transform-load (ETL) pipelines; (v) data preprocessing transformations. It should be noted that in general CAWs are not limited to only these types of workflows and HITL services permit their extension to other types. In the ExtremeXP framework, CAWs are represented via Domain Specific Language (DSL) documented in D2.1 and serialized via .xpf file format, also documented in more detail in D5.1.

Variability points. A variability point is an aspect of the CAW that can be changed and can refer to (i) different task implementations (e.g., different ML algorithms), (ii) different task inputs (e.g., different datasets), (iii) different hyperparameters, (iv) different task/workflow deployments (e.g., on CPUs/GPUs). Each variability point has a domain that defines a set or range of its possible values.

User. The users of the ExtremeXP framework are data analysts or domain experts with a vested interest in the development and operation of a CAW. In the case of HITL services, the users are typically domain experts, without high technical skills, thus relying on high task automation and human-friendly environment.

Intent. An intent in ExtremeXP is a specification of the expected result of the CAW, in the preselected options or in the form of a natural language prompt, e.g., *"I want to classify input log data to detect malware activity on my network"* (UC2) or *"I want to find the best classifier in order to detect manufacturing machine anomalies in time-series data"* (UC5).

- **Constraints.** Intents can further be accompanied with some design-time (e.g., *"limit the complexity of CAW to minimum mandatory"*) or run-time constraints (e.g., *"accuracy over 80%"*).
- **Preferences.** Users may also define their preferences with regard to the created CAW (e.g., *"using only XGBoost algorithm"*).

User profile. Based on the interaction of the users within the system, a structured representation of a user's preferences, behaviors, feedback, and characteristics is collected and user profiles are created to represent users and thus allow more customized environment and intent anticipation.

User feedback. Provides end users' sentiment about the produced CAW and the obtained results. Such feedback contains users' level of satisfaction that complements the relation among users, their intents, and the produced CAWs.

¹ <https://www.knime.com/>

² <https://scikit-learn.org/>

2.2 Semantic-based backbone (Knowledge Graph)

Leveraging knowledge graphs (KG) and ontologies provides a powerful foundation for automating different tasks within the HITL services. By structuring data in machine readable manner enriched with semantic meaning of domain vocabularies, knowledge graphs enable creation of automatable modules that can heavily benefit from relationships represented in the data, detect patterns, and infer new insights beyond raw data and metadata. Knowledge Graphs allow processes such as classification, recommendation, and decision support to be executed with minimal manual intervention, leveraging both explicit domain knowledge and inferred patterns. Moreover, their adaptability ensures that as new data and concepts emerge, the system can incorporate them consistently, thereby fostering scalable, transparent, and explainable automation.

In the case of HITL services KG represents the main semantic-based backbone of the module by incorporating all domain-specific metadata information, necessary for smooth and automated functioning of the module. In Figure 1, we present the diagram of the main knowledge graph concepts (classes) defined for HITL services. This KG is based on the extensive literature review and the existing Data Mining OPTimization Ontology (DMOP) [9] has been adopted and extended for the context of the HITL services within the ExtremeXP framework. The central focus of the KG is the **Workflow** class, representing the CAW being generated from input user **Intent** to satisfy a specific **Task** and consisting of one or more ordered **Steps**, each implementing a specific **Algorithm** or a **Process**. On the other side, another important class is **User** who participates in the definition of the **Intent**, and running of the generated **Workflow**, and based on the obtained results providing **User Feedback**. Workflow uses an input **Dataset**, which in addition stores necessary metadata in terms of **Dataset Characteristics** that describe closely the data being used in the process. In addition, each **Task** has associated **Evaluation Requirement** specifying the **Method** and **Metric** being used for evaluating the generated model. Similarly, a task can also have an associated **Constraint** together with its expected **Value**, previously expressed by the user.

Figure 1: Knowledge graph backbone for HITL services

3. Capturing and automated mapping of user intents to complex analytics workflows (T4.3)

In this section, we provide a detailed description of the Intent Specification to Workflow Generation Framework (I2WG), outlining its different execution steps and giving an extensive look to the ontology design.

3.1 General Overview

The objective of the Intent Specification to Workflow Generation Framework (I2WG) is to allow non-expert users to generate complex analytics workflows for their data analysis. To do so, the users specify their requirements through analytical intents, high-level descriptions of the task to undertake.

The approach followed here to automatically generate analytical workflows is the use of a knowledge-graph-based ontology to represent the workflows in an abstract way, and harness the semantic power provided by this ontology to make possible the generation of valid workflows. First, a new ontology has been developed to represent such Complex Analytics Workflows (CAWs), as well as the rest of the concepts needed to capture intents, allowing all of them to be represented with the same vocabulary. While introducing new concepts, it reuses several elements from pre-existing ontologies, such as the family of Algorithms and Problems, and the way to represent IO Objects (i.e., input and output assets of CAW processing steps), which are taken from the DMOP ontology. The main novel contributions of the ontology are the pre- and post-conditions of the Components, which are expressed through Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL) [1] Shapes; and the Transformations, which are implemented with embedded SPARQL Insert/Delete statements.

Figure 2 depicts the execution pipeline of I2WG, which is divided into four general phases: dataset annotator, abstract planner, logical planner, and workflow translator.

1. The dataset annotator phase receives a raw data file and builds a knowledge graph with the information gathered. This information includes number of columns, number of rows and column-specific indicators, such as missing value percentage or whether it contains normalized data. This new representation is leveraged in the next execution phases. With data represented in a proper format, the user can create intents. An intent includes a data graph and a task to tackle. Additionally, it might include extra information related to the task, like target column for classification problems. An example of a valid intent could be to perform classification over the titanic dataset.
2. With the intent defined, the abstract planner can be executed. The goal of this step is to generate high-level versions of the final workflows. This serves as a draft to see how the final workflow will look like. These abstract plans are constructed using the information provided by the knowledge graph ontology and, rather than specific implementations, they are built using the generalized task (i.e., model training instead of specifying the model to employ).
3. The next execution step is the logical planner. Here, the knowledge contained in the ontology is used to refine the abstract plans and generate analytical workflows. During this refinement process, the high-level elements (e.g., partitioning) are changed for specific components (e.g., random relative train test split). A different workflow is generated for each component combination that can solve the desired task.
4. The produced workflows cannot be executed directly by I2WG. Instead, the last step, workflow translator, translates them to other formats that are supported by external tools.

Figure 2: End-to-end pipeline to generate complex analytics workflows from intents

3.2 Ontology design

This section details the contents and structure of the ontology that I2WG uses to support the execution of Abstract Planner, Logical Planner, and Workflow translator. An ontology is a formal representation of knowledge within a specific domain. This knowledge is expressed as a set of concepts (nodes) and the relations between them (properties). It provides a structured framework for understanding and organizing information, often through a hierarchy or taxonomy.

A common approach to structure the knowledge in an ontology is by dividing the concepts and properties into a Terminological Box (TBOX) and an Assertional Box (ABOX). The TBOX contains the definition of existing concepts, relationships, and properties. In other words, it represents the schema of the domain. In contrast, the ABOX contains the instances of the classes defined in the TBOX and their actual properties and relationships. In some cases, the ontology contains concepts that do not naturally belong to the TBOX or the ABOX. The I2WG ontology uses an extra layer to represent this knowledge: Controlled Vocabularies Box (CBOX).

In the I2WG ontology, the elements depicted in the TBOX and the CBOX represent the knowledge that the framework has a priori, while elements in the ABOX are created by the framework at execution time. The ontology is represented using OWL DL language. It is used for two main reasons: some axioms that the ontology uses, such as **owl:disjointWith**, are unavailable in other DLs like OWL Lite, and OWL DL is also the DL Language used by DMOP, which is part of the I2WG ontology. To reinforce the layer separation, each level has a different URI prefix: TBOX uses **tb**, CBOX uses **cb** and ABOX uses **ab**.

3.2.1 TBOX

In this section we provide the most relevant concepts and relationships present in the TBOX layer of the I2WG ontology. Figure 3 depicts the ontology concepts.

Figure 3: I2WG TBOX concepts

Intent-related concepts

The concept of **Intent** represents the intentions of the user. These intentions include a dataset (represented by *overData* property), the values specified for certain parameters (*specifiesValue* property) and either a task or an algorithm (*specifies* property).

The **Data** node represents the dataset used within the workflow generation. It is used to represent the base (annotated) dataset that the user provides, but it is also used to represent the intermediate results created in each step of the workflow generation. This class is equivalent to the DM-Data class defined in the DMOP ontology.

The **Task** concept represents the task provided by the user through the intent definition (*tackles* property). Task encapsulates all possible data mining processes that can be performed in the data. Moreover, some tasks can be segmented into smaller ones. For instance, *Descriptive Analysis* includes *Data Cleaning* and *Data Visualization*. These task dependencies are represented through the *subtaskOf* property.

Algorithm-related concepts

The **Algorithm** class represents all possible solutions to solve a certain *task*. For example, SVM algorithm is suitable for solving classification tasks, whereas KMeans algorithm solves clustering problems.

The concept of **Implementation** represents a specific executable version of an *algorithm*. Hence, an adaptation of an algorithm to a certain programming language. It includes the parameters that

implementations accept and defines their input and output requirements through *specifiesInput/specifiesOutput* properties.

DataTag represents a particular data characteristic. It is expressed as SHACL shapes. As an example of a *dataTag*, *NormalizedTabularDatasetShape* is satisfied by data if it has tabular format and *dmop:isNormalized* property is true.

DataSpec serves as a *dataTag* aggregator. As each input requirement can have multiple *dataTags*, *dataSpec* is created to represent a complex data requirement. For example, SVM implementation has an input *dataSpec* with normalized data and no missing values as input requirements.

A **Component** represents an implementation with specific parameter values. Different components can be created based on the same implementation to account for different parameter presets.

There exist some parameters whose value cannot be established beforehand. This is the case, for example, of the target data column parameter or the file input path present in data reader implementations. These parameters are linked with *exposesParameter* property and are defined among the intent information. With *hasTransformation* property, a component is linked with its transformations that control the input-output data flow. Components are sometimes related to heuristic rules through *hasRule* that can be used to rank their performance for a given data and task.

The concept of **Rule** represents the heuristic rules used to select the best component given a task and a set of data characteristics. The properties *relatedToTag* and *relatedToTask* store the aforementioned relationships.

The **Transformation** concept depicts the data transformations that are produced inside the components (represented through *hasTransformation* property in Figure 3). Some components return an altered version of the dataset provided as input. This is the case of all the preprocessing components. For example, a normalizer component should return an updated version of the input specifying that the data is now normalized. Note that this process does not normalize the data but modifies the data graph assuming it was done.

The **Parameter** concept represents the hyperparameters that can be tuned for each implementation of a certain algorithm. **ParameterSpecification** is used to link a parameter with a specific value that a component establishes. The **ParameterValue** concept resembles *ParameterSpecification*, but in this case, it links a parameter with a specific value established by the intent configurations, not a component.

Workflow-related concepts

The **Step** concept is created to establish the order of the component execution. It is connected with a component through the *runs* property. It is also connected with the next step within the same workflow through the *followedBy* property. Each step has connections with the parameters used by the component through *usesParameter* property. Via *hasInput* and *hasOutput* properties, each step is linked to its input and output data.

The **Workflow** class represents the set of steps that should be executed over a provided dataset to accomplish the user intentions. It is connected to the intent concept through *generatedFor*. It is also connected to the set of steps that constitute it using *hasStep* property.

3.3 I2WG pipeline

This section discusses in detail the different execution phases present in I2WG.

3.3.1 Dataset annotator

Figure 4: Dataset annotator overview

The goal of the dataset annotator is to extract information from a given raw file (e.g., CSV, parquet file, tensors) to create a graph representation with it. This data graph representation is used in the next execution steps to get an insight of the data characteristics.

When receiving a CSV file as input, the dataset annotator transforms it to a pandas dataframe. This is a straightforward step, as pandas directly provides a function to load data from CSV files.

With the data structured as a dataframe, the tabular annotator phase (i.e., a special case of dataset annotator for tabular data inputs) can be executed. Here is where the information extraction process is done. The dataset annotator extracts three kinds of information:

- Metadata: information like filename, file path, delimiter, etc.
- General data: metrics of the whole dataset such as the number of columns, number of rows, outliers, etc.
- Column data: information about individual columns such as column type, missing values, feature type, etc.

The extracted information is stored in a knowledge graph that will complement the information contained in the ontology. For convenience, the graph is returned serialized as a turtle file that can be reloaded later.

Note that this step is not required to be executed each time a user creates a new intent. It should only be executed when the dataset used is new. The turtle files produced by the dataset annotator can be reused as long as the original files do not change.

To further illustrate this process, let us consider a real-world example. Suppose a user wants to test I2WG using the Titanic dataset. Upon uploading the file, the dataset annotator transforms the data into a pandas dataframe and then extracts the relevant information using the Tabular Annotator. A fragment of the resulting dataset graph is depicted in Figure 5.

```

ab:titanic a dmop:TabularDataset ;
  dmop:containsOutliers true ;
  dmop:fileFormat "CSV" ;
  dmop:hasColumn ab:Age,
    ab:Cabin,
  dmop:isNormallyDistributed true ;
  dmop:missingvaluesPercentage 7.95e-01 ;
  dmop:numberOfColumns 12 ;
  dmop:numberOfRows 891 ;

ab:Age a dmop:Column ;
  dmop:containsNulls true ;
  dmop:hasColumnName "Age" ;
  dmop:hasDataPrimitiveTypeColumn dmop:Float ;
  dmop:hasOutliers true ;
  dmop:isFeature true ;
  dmop:isLabel false ;
  dmop:isNormalDistribution true ;
  dmop:isUnique false .

ab:Cabin a dmop:Column ;
  
```

Figure 5: Fragment of data set graph produced for titanic dataset

3.3.2 Abstract planner

Figure 6: Abstract planner overview

The aim of the abstract planner (Figure 6) phase is to obtain a high-level representation of the workflows that will be produced in the next steps with the information present in the user intent.

To execute the abstract planner and the following steps, an intent must be created. To do so, the user needs to provide a task to tackle, and a dataset graph previously generated using the dataset annotator. Depending on the type of task, more information might be needed. In the case of classification tasks, the user also needs to specify what dataset column will be used as target.

In the first phase, “*get algorithms*”, the abstract planner uses the knowledge present in the ontology to get all the known algorithms capable of solving the task specified in the intent.

The next phase, “*get implementations*”, consists of finding all the implementations depicted in the ontology of the previously found algorithms. As an example, for XGBoost (i.e., an eXtreme Gradient Boosting classification algorithm), two implementations are found: XGBoost Tree and XGBoost Linear.

For each implementation found, an abstract plan is produced. The abstract plan is a simple workflow that anticipates the structure of the final generated workflows by using high-level component representations. These workflows serve as a base point for the next step. As an extra benefit, these intermediate results can be used by the users to discard approaches and speed up the remaining tasks.

To illustrate this phase, let us consider again the Titanic dataset. Assuming that the data graph has already been generated, an intent involving this data can be created. A valid intent created by a user could be, for example, tackling a classification task over the titanic dataset with *Survived* as target variable.

With that intent, the abstract planner will look for suitable algorithms to solve classification problems. Some of the possibilities are decision tree, SVM, NN or XGBoost Tree. Next, for each algorithm, all the suitable implementations will be retrieved from the ontology. Finally, the abstract plans are created by concatenating data loading, partitioning and data storing to each implementation found. Figure 7 shows one of the abstract plans produced. In this case, the one created for decision trees. Notice that these components at the abstract plan level act as placeholders for possible implementations found, while different implementations for each component will yield a new variability point.

Figure 7: Abstract plan for decision tree

3.3.3 Logical planner

Figure 8: Logical planner overview

The logical planner (Figure 8) aims to create complex analytics workflows from a given set of abstract plans and intent information. This phase is divided into two different subphases: combination explorer and workflow builder.

The Combination explorer finds all the possible component combinations that can fulfil the intent requirements. Each combination found is expressed as a component sequence, an ordered list that dictates what components need to be executed and the order of execution.

Many of the implementations present in the ontology have some kind of data dependencies that need to be fulfilled to work as expected. For example, SVM highly benefits from normalized data.

The Combination explorer considers the data requirements of the main implementations (i.e., the ones capable of solving the task specified in the intent). For each of the requirements, the combination explorer checks if the data already satisfies the conditions. If the dependency is not satisfied, it looks for an implementation that can transform the data to fulfill the requirements. For example, normalizer implementation is capable of normalizing numerical features from the data. Hence, If the original data is not normalized, a normalization step will be added before the SVM step in the component sequence.

These requirements are expressed using SHACL. This language is designed for validating RDF graphs against a set of conditions. In this case, the dataset graph is validated against the implementation requirements, that are expressed as node shapes.

To improve performance, the ontology provides a set of heuristic rules that reduce the search space for components. These rules rank the components depending on the data and task. Then, only the top ranked ones are chosen.

The component sequence is then transformed into analytical workflows with the workflow builder. Workflow builder considers each element in the component sequence as a different step. The order of the steps is also aligned with the position in the component sequence. For each step, a new output dataset is created by executing the component transformations over the input dataset.

Let us consider the titanic example again to illustrate the execution of the logical planner. At the end, 40 different plans are generated. The variability points are the different components and implementations of the algorithms that solve classification problems and the four equally ranked partitioning components. Figure 9 shows one of the generated component sequences for this example.

Figure 9: Logical plan for titanic dataset classification

If the plan depicted in Figure 7 is provided as input to the workflow builder, the result obtained will be an extended version of what is shown in Figure 10. Note that each step corresponds to one of the components depicted in Figure 9.

```

ab:workflow_16_Titanic a tb:Workflow ;
  tb:generatedFor ab:TitanicIntent ;
  tb:hasStep ab:workflow_16_Titanic-step_0_component_csv_local_reader,
    ab:workflow_16_Titanic-step_1_component_random_relative_train_test_split,
    ab:workflow_16_Titanic-step_2_component_mean_imputation,
    ab:workflow_16_Titanic-step_3_component_missing_value_management_applier,
    ab:workflow_16_Titanic-step_4_component_xgboost_tree_learner,
    ab:workflow_16_Titanic-step_5_component_xgboost_predictor,
    ab:workflow_16_Titanic-step_6_component_csv_local_writer ;
  tb:knimeCompatible true .

ab:workflow_16_Titanic-step_0_component_csv_local_reader a tb:Step ;
  tb:followedBy ab:workflow_16_Titanic-step_1_component_random_relative_train_test_split ;
  tb:hasOutput [ a tb:Data ;
    tb:has_data ab:workflow_16_Titanic-original_dataset ;
    tb:has_position 0 ] ;
  tb:has_position 0 ;
  tb:runs cb:component-csv_local_reader ;
  tb:usesParameter cb:implementation-csv_reader-append_path_column_internals,

```

Figure 10: Fragment workflow graph generated for titanic dataset classification

3.3.4 Workflow translator

Figure 11: Workflow translator overview

The last step in the execution pipeline of the I2WG framework is the workflow translator (Figure 11). In this phase, the workflows produced by the logical planner are translated to other formats. More precisely, I2WG supports translation to KNIME workflows.

KNIME translator uses the knowledge graph ontology to retrieve the KNIME engine-specific information. This includes getting the parameters and equivalences between I2WG components and KNIME components.

RDF translator simply serializes the workflow graph to turtle format. With this translation, the workflows can be stored, and, at any time, they can serve as input for the workflow translator and be exported to other formats.

Considering the Titanic example for the last time, with the workflow generated by the logical planner depicted in (Figure 9), workflow translator can be used to generate a KNIME compatible workflow. Figure 12 shows the KNIME representation of the translated workflow.

Figure 12: KNIME workflow for titanic dataset classification

3.4 Evaluation

3.4.1 Use case validation

In this section we evaluate I2WG with real use cases from cybersecurity (i2Cat - UC2) and manufacturing (IDEKO - UC5) domains.

The aim of the cybersecurity use case, provided by I2Cat, is to predict whether an agent is compromised by using user telemetry. To solve the requirements of this use case, the first step is to upload the data to I2WG and annotate it. After that, an intent can be created specifying the data previously uploaded, selecting classification as the desired task, and choosing malicious label as the target variable. When executed, it produces workflows like the one depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Workflow produced for cybersecurity use case

Then, the generated workflow is translated to .xnp format so it can be executed on that particular engine. The obtained file is depicted in Figure 14. Mainly, it defines the tasks present in the workflow, the order of appearance and the input data path. It generates one workflow construct per combination considered.

```

workflow Workflow_4 {
  define task DataLoading;
  define task Partitioning;
  define task ModelTrain;
  define task ModelPredict;
  define task DataStoring;

  START -> DataLoading -> Partitioning -> ModelTrain -> ModelPredict -> DataStoring -> END;

  task DataLoading {
    implementation "DemoIntent.data_reader_component";
  }
  task Partitioning {
    implementation "DemoIntent.top_k_absolute_train_test_split";
  }
  task ModelTrain {
    implementation "DemoIntent.xgboost_linear_learner";
  }
  task ModelPredict {
    implementation "DemoIntent.xgboost_linear_learner_predictor";
  }
  task DataStoring {
    implementation "DemoIntent.data_writer_component";
  }

  define input data InputData;
  configure data InputData {
    path "./T1016_SystemNetworkConfigurationDiscovery"}
}
    
```

Figure 14: Cybersecurity use case output example

Similarly, the goal of the manufacturing use case, provided by IDEKO, is to create a multiclass classification model to perform machine failure prediction. In this case, the input is a tensor, thus Dataset Annotator expects a file in npz format. In the concrete case of UC5, in order to upload the data files into the Dataset Annotator, first, a custom script needs to be executed to transform the folder-csv format to npz format, and then the data will be properly annotated. With data uploaded on I2WG, the intent can be created by also specifying that the task that should be solved is classification and the target variable is IDEKO_Y. Figure 15 shows one of the produced workflows.

Figure 15: Workflow produced for manufacturing use case

In this case, workflows are also desired to be translated to XXP format. The final result is shown in Figure 16. The workflow representation resembles the one obtained for cybersecurity use case. However, note that the partitioning and NN tasks use tensor-specific implementation rather than the tabular components used for cybersecurity use case.

```

workflow Workflow_3 {

  define task DataLoading;
  define task Partitioning;
  define task NN;
  define task DataStoring;

  START -> DataLoading -> Partitioning -> NN -> DataStoring -> END;

  task DataLoading {
    implementation "DemoIntent.data_reader_component"; }
  task Partitioning {
    implementation "DemoIntent.random_relative_train_test_split_(tensor)";}
  task NN {
    implementation "DemoIntent.convolutional_nn_multidimensional_learner";}
  task DataStoring {
    implementation "DemoIntent.data_writer_component";}

  define input data InputData;
  configure data InputData {
    path "./datasets/IDEKO.npz" }}

```

Figure 16: Manufacturing use case output example

By using I2WG, IDEKO and I2Cat are able to automate the generation of machine learning pipelines that are useful for their use cases. The workflows produced serve as a basepoint for generating the model and are further sent to the Experimentation Engine of the ExtremeXP platform.

3.4.2 Time performance

As explained above, I2WG is composed of four components: dataset annotator, abstract planner, logical planner, and workflow translator.

Dataset annotator creates a profile of the dataset. To do so, it goes through all the data to compute useful metrics. The execution time grows linearly with the number of observations and features of the dataset.

Abstract planner usually provides the response in real time, as it only checks what algorithms can solve the specified task. Hence, the execution grows linearly with the number of algorithms present in the ontology.

Workflow translator also provides the response in real time. The translation process does not involve any time-consuming task, as it uses the knowledge graph to translate the already created workflow. Its execution time grows linearly with the number of steps and parameters present in the already generated workflow.

The most time-consuming phase of I2WG is, by far, the logical planner. In this phase, the tool generates workflows for all combinations, which is expensive, or even infeasible due to combinatorial explosion.

The logical planner execution time depends on two factors: the number of data columns and the ontology complexity. It is worth noting that the number of observations present in a dataset does not affect the execution time of the logical planner, as the annotated dataset only contains general aggregated statistics for each feature (i.e., number of nulls, whether data is normalized, etc.), rather than raw observation data.

To get an insight of the execution time of the logical planner in different contexts, this phase of the I2WG framework has been executed for two datasets with different numbers of columns and various ontologies with a different degree of complexity.

Section 3.4.2.1 offers more details of how these ontologies had been generated, Section 3.4.2.2 offers insights into the chosen datasets and Section 3.4.2.3 shows the results obtained.

3.4.2.1 *Ontology generation*

As explained before, the ontology complexity affects the execution time of the logical planner of I2WG. To quantify this impact, ontologies of different complexity levels must be generated. However, this generation presents serious challenges. The main one is how to quantify ontology complexity.

An assumption made is that more complex ontologies offer more possibilities to solve a task than a simpler one. In other words, as the ontology complexity increases, the number of workflow combinations generated should also increase.

Generating complex ontologies is not as easy as creating random implementations with random input and output requirements. If this approach is followed, very few or even no logical plans would be generated. This happens due to unsatisfactory input requirements caused by the random generation.

Another important consideration when dealing with random input and output requirements, is the undesired livelocks that can appear when searching for workflow combinations.

A livelock can occur if two implementations can satisfy each other's input requirements. For example, implementation B having as input requirement shape0 and shape1 as output. If there exists some implementation A that has shape1 as input requirement and shape0 as output, a livelock will occur. This example is depicted in Figure 17.

Figure 17: *Livelock example*

Livelocks can cause a reduction for possible combinations, but the main impact is in terms of performance. The recursive algorithm explores all the possible combinations and gets stuck if a livelock occurs.

Following the aforementioned livelock example, the generation algorithm would assemble a possible plan like implementation A → implementation B → implementation A → implementation B →...

The algorithm would never naturally end, so the MAX_PLAN_LENGTH global variable is introduced to control the maximum number of steps a plan can have, ensuring the algorithm always finishes.

This approach, however, implies that when a livelock occurs, the execution is not immediately truncated. Instead, it is done when the maximum number of steps is reached, slowing down performance. Considering that livelocks should be rare in practice, the approach followed for the generation of the ontologies ensures that no livelocks will be generated. Additionally, it also guarantees that all input requirements can be satisfied.

To control the complexity, the ontology generation is driven by two parameters: maximum depth level and components per implementation (CPI). The generation algorithm works as follows:

1. Create an implementation that solves classification tasks (main implementation) with two input shapes, shape0 and shape1.
2. Generate two new implementations with shape0 and shape1 as output shapes, respectively. (depth level 0)
3. For each of the implementations generated on the last depth level, create two new input shapes. For each shape created, add a new implementation with it as output. (depth level n)
4. Repeat step 3 until maximum depth level is reached.
5. For each implementation generated in the last depth level, create a new input shape. For each shape created, add a new implementation with it as output. (base level)
6. For each implementation generated outside the base level, create CPI components. For implementations on the base level, generate only one.

Figure 18 depicts how the generated ontologies look like by showing the dependence graph between implementations.

Figure 18: Example of generated ontology with depth level = 2 and CPI = 1. Each node represents a different implementation and each edge an input-output shape requirement between them

For the evaluation task, 4 different ontologies have been created: Two with depth=0 and CPI=1 and CPI=2 respectively, and two with depth=1 and CPI=2 and CPI=3 respectively.

3.4.2.2 Datasets

To benchmark I2WG, two different datasets have been considered: titanic and cybersecurity. These datasets are chosen for the difference in the number of features.

The titanic dataset contains information about the passengers aboard the RMS Titanic, which sank on its first voyage in 1912. This dataset only has 12 features.

The cybersecurity dataset is the one provided by I2Cat for the cybersecurity use case (UC2). It has already been used to evaluate the utility of the tool. It is also useful for this task for its considerable number of features, 266.

3.4.2.3 Results

For every combination of ontology and dataset, the performance metrics of I2WG have been recorded (i.e., *Execution time* of the logical planner phase of I2WG, the number of *Generated workflows*, and the throughput of generated *workflows per second*).

Table 1 depicts the results obtained for the titanic dataset. On the other hand, Table 2 shows the results for the cybersecurity dataset. The execution times present in both tables have been obtained by averaging the results of four different executions of the logical planner. Additionally, the tables also show the number of workflows generated per case, and the generation speed.

These experiments have been executed on a Windows 11 machine with 11th Gen Intel Core i5-1135G7 2.40GHz CPU and 8GB of RAM.

Depth levels	CPI	Execution time (seconds)	Generated workflows	Workflows/s
0	1	1.19	1	0.878
0	2	7.17	8	1.116
1	2	211.63	128	0.605
1	3	3457.10	2187	0.633

Table 1: Execution time in seconds, generated workflows, and speed for *Titanic dataset*

Depth levels	CPI	Execution time (seconds)	Generated workflows	Workflows/s
0	1	1.21	1	0.825
0	2	6.91	8	1.158
1	2	216.02	128	0.592
1	3	3756.89	2187	0.582

Table 2: Execution time in seconds, generated workflows, and speed for *UC2 dataset*

Comparing the results of Table 1 and Table 2 shows that the number of features has no considerable impact on the global execution time of the I2WG. In the worst case, CPI=3 and depth = 1, the difference in execution time is five minutes. For the other cases, the difference is much smaller.

Unlike dataset features, the results show that ontology complexity has a major influence on execution time. When the ontology gets more complex, the number of possible component combinations grows. As it can be seen with depth=1, when CPI=2 the execution time is about 3 minutes and 30 seconds. However, if CPI is increased up to 3, the execution time increases up to 1 hour.

The use of design constraints can dramatically reduce the number of generated workflows, as it excludes implementations, components and algorithms from being considered. Moreover, the max importance level parameter can also reduce the number of evaluated shapes and, thus, the workflow complexity. Finally, heuristic rules help maintain CPI value low and, with that, the number of combinations considered.

It is also worth noting that the growth rate of generated workflows is not linear, rather it is exponential. The number of possible combinations rapidly grows when the ontology complexity is increased. With very complex ontologies, the number of combinations could be prohibitive to

generate. This problem can be mitigated by reducing the search space with constraints and heuristics as well as by tuning the complexity parameter.

Another interesting result is that the workflow generation speed stabilizes when the number of generated workflows is big. Hence, we can say that the process of generating a workflow given a combination is constant.

3.4.3 Quality assessment

The aim of this section is to assess the quality of the workflows produced by I2WG in comparison to naïve automated approaches (i.e., without considering preprocessing steps). Unfortunately, this evaluation cannot be done directly into the framework, as it does not support workflow execution. Hence, it is not possible to obtain accuracy or precision metrics directly. Instead, the workflows should be executed in an external engine.

For this experiment, I2WG has been tested using popular datasets for binary classification. For each dataset, one representative generated workflow has been exported to KNIME. The chosen workflow is always the one with polynomial SVM as main component and with random relative split strategy.

Using KNIME, each exported workflow has been executed as is, without any modifications. Figure 19 shows one of these generated workflows imported to KNIME.

Figure 19: Generated I2WG workflow to solve binary classification for Penguins dataset

For each dataset, a minimal workflow (i.e., without additional preprocessing steps) has also been created and executed using KNIME. With the results obtained, F1 scores have been computed as well. These minimal workflows aim to represent the simplest pipeline that can solve the classification task. In this case, all minimal workflows consist of csv reader, partitioning with default configurations, polynomial SVM learner, SVM predictor, and csv writer. An example of minimal workflow is shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Naïve workflow created for Penguins dataset

With the two F1 scores, it is possible to assess whether the complete workflows generated with I2WG produce better results than the ones obtained with naïve automated pipeline orchestration. The results obtained are summarized in Table 3.

Binary classification dataset	F1 score (minimal workflow)	F1 score (I2WG workflow)
Titanic ³	0.485	0.716
Penguins [73]	0.978	1.0
Diabetes ⁴	0.771	0.821
Breast [74]	0.581	0.971

Table 3: Performance results of a minimal workflow versus the I2WG workflow per dataset

For all the datasets, the F1 score of the I2WG is always higher than the one computed from the naïve approach. The most remarkable improvements are from the Titanic and Breast cancer dataset.

Despite the limitations of the experiment, only one type of model and 4 datasets, it illustrates that the complexity that I2WG adds to the workflow generation, compared to a minimal approach, improves the quality of the results. In other words, the workflows produced by I2WG can provide satisfactory results.

³ <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/yasserh/titanic-dataset>

⁴ <https://search.r-project.org/CRAN/refmans/mlbench/html/PimaIndiansDiabetes.html>

4. User profile and context prediction for intent anticipation (T4.4)

Task 4.4, User profile and context prediction for intent anticipation, addresses the challenge of understanding and predicting user analytical intents in complex analytics environments. The objective is to capture user intents and constraints in a structured manner, represent them within a Knowledge Graph (KG), and exploit this representation to recommend future intents in a way that is adaptive. The work carried out in this task has been structured around five interrelated components, each of which has led to dedicated research outputs and publications.

The first step involves the *automatic capturing and classification of analytical intents*, where we focus on identifying the intents underlying user interactions with analytical systems. By detecting and categorizing these intents, we establish the foundation for modelling user behaviour in a way that goes beyond surface-level actions.

Complementing this, the *automatic capturing and classification of constraints* enables us to take into account the conditions, limitations, or preferences that shape how users approach analytical tasks. Constraints, together with intents, form a holistic picture of the user's analytical context.

Once intents and constraints are captured, they need to be grounded in a structured representation. This is achieved through the *mapping of intents and constraints to knowledge graph concepts*. By anchoring user goals and requirements to a semantic backbone, we enable interoperability, querying, reasoning, and alignment with domain knowledge.

Building on this semantic representation, we then explore *intent anticipation via knowledge graph embeddings*. By leveraging embedding techniques, the system can predict and recommend likely next intents, facilitating proactive assistance and improving the user experience. This step bridges the gap between static modelling of behaviour and dynamic anticipation of future needs.

Finally, we address the critical issue of *maintenance and updates of knowledge graph embeddings*, ensuring that the recommendation mechanisms remain accurate and relevant as new data, contexts, and user behaviours emerge. This adaptive capability is key to sustaining long-term performance and robustness.

Together, these five components form an integrated pipeline: starting with capturing user intents and constraints, grounding them in knowledge graphs, using embeddings for recommendation, and maintaining the embeddings over time. The results reported here provide not only scientific advances, demonstrated in the accompanying publications, but also concrete contributions to the project's overarching goal of predictive and context-aware user profiling.

4.1 Automatic Capturing and Classification of Analytical Intents

This subsection addresses the problem of identifying and classifying analytical intents expressed by users in data analysis scenarios. In such scenarios, a user is expected to specify the purpose or type of the analysis (e.g., classification, regression, clustering, etc.), which we refer to as analytical intent. This initial step becomes challenging when users do not know how to translate an analytical intent or a business question into data analytics terms. Nevertheless, they do know how to express the purpose of their analysis in text, even if it is a high-level domain-focused description. Hence, in this work we explore the possibility of capturing the underlying analytical intents from textual problem descriptions, so that an analytical workflow can be generated without any further compulsory user interaction. The work advances existing taxonomies of intents, explores the potential of Large Language Models (LLMs) for automatic analytical intent classification, and introduces a systematic methodology for generating validation data. Together, these contributions establish a foundation for intent anticipation within user profiles, as required by Task 4.4.

4.1.1 Categorization of Analytical Intents

The categorization of analytical intents proposed in [4] does not fully capture the diversity of users' analytical needs. To address this, we developed an expanded hierarchical structure. The top layer groups general intents, inspired by [3], while the second layer specifies concrete analytical tasks. The automatic classifier is designed to predict labels at this second level, thereby producing results that are both specific and actionable for the selection of suitable data analytics methods.

The intents (Figure 21) are organised into five categories:

- **Describe:** providing descriptive views of dataset instances or variables, supported by techniques such as Data Profiling (DP) and Clustering (CL).
- **Assess:** identifying discrepancies, correlations, or associations, including methods such as Correlation Analysis (CA), Anomaly Detection (AD), and Association Rule Mining (AR).
- **Explain:** uncovering causal relationships through Causal Inference (CI).
- **Predict:** forecasting events or estimating probabilities, using Classification (CS), Regression (RE), and Forecasting (FC) techniques.
- **Suggest:** guiding future actions based on the outcomes of the previous categories.

This categorization also maps naturally to established types of data analytics [2]: *Describe* aligns with descriptive analytics, *Assess* and *Explain* with diagnostic analytics, *Predict* with predictive analytics, and *Suggest* with prescriptive analytics.

Figure 21: Intent Categorization

4.1.2 On the Use of LLMs for Automatic Intent Classification

A range of text classification techniques with different modelling requirements was evaluated for the task of intent classification. Using the validation set from [4], which includes clustering (CL), prediction (PR), and frequent pattern mining (FPM) intents, we compared three approaches:

- A high-effort classifier from [4], based on FastText embeddings, LSTM, GRU, and SVM models trained on 22,000 instances.
- Medium-effort approaches using pre-trained LLMs (BERT, RoBERTa) with fine-tuned linear classification layers.
- Low-effort prompting-based methods using generative LLMs with designed prompts, including open-source and proprietary models of different sizes.

The results (Table 4) show that BERT-based models outperform or match the performance of the best ensemble method in [4], while LLM prompting significantly improves accuracy—even with relatively small open-source models. These findings demonstrate that LLMs are not only the best performing approach, but also the most efficient in terms of modelling effort.

Classifier	Precision			Recall			Accuracy
	CL	FPM	PR	CL	FPM	PR	
TbIAS [4]	1.00	0.79	0.86	0.70	0.95	0.95	0.87
BERT	1.00	0.79	0.90	0.75	0.95	0.90	0.87
RoBERTa	1.00	0.95	0.87	0.85	0.95	1.00	0.93
GPT-4	1.00	1.00	0.91	0.95	0.95	1.00	0.97
Mistral-7b-instruct	1.00	0.87	1.00	0.95	1.00	0.90	0.95

Table 4: Preliminary Intent Classification Evaluation

Motivated by these results, we extended the analysis with newly generated validation datasets and a broader categorization of intents. A systematic pipeline was designed (Figure 22), covering intent definition, data generation, and validation through LLM predictions.

Figure 22: A systematic method for the validation of analytical intent text classifiers

4.1.3 Validation Data Collection

To overcome the lack of suitable benchmark datasets, we developed a four-step pipeline: **Data Collection, Preprocessing, Label Verification, and Label Masking**. This approach can be adapted to different sources, provided a data connector is available.

- **Data Collection:** Using query-based retrieval, datasets were gathered from Kaggle and Cross Validated, resulting in KG-QA and CV-QA datasets, and from Kaggle competitions, producing the KG-Comp dataset (Table 5).
- **Preprocessing:** Non-textual elements such as code snippets and images were removed. Only English-language documents and the initial user-authored content were retained.
- **Label Verification:** A manual expert-based process was implemented to ensure high-quality validation labels. Rules were established to exclude irrelevant or noisy documents. Table 6 shows the number of files retrieved, discarded, and retained per class.
- **Label Masking:** To reduce classification bias, occurrences of class-specific keywords were systematically replaced with synonyms (e.g., “correlation” → “interdependence”), leveraging WordNet [5] and thesaurus resources.

Class	KG-QA	KG-Comp	CV-QA
DP	-	-	[data-visualization] or [descriptive-statistics]
CL	clustering	clustering	[clustering]
CA	correlation	-	[correlation]
AD	anomaly detection	anomaly detection	[anomaly-detection]
AR	-	-	[association-rules]
CI	-	-	[causality]
RE	regression	regression	[regression] and [predictive-models]
CS	classification	classification	[classification] and [predictive-models]
FC	forecasting	forecasting	[forecasting] and [predictive-models]

Table 5: Search queries for the three validation datasets. “-” means that no textual statements were found for the corresponding class (intent).

Class	KG-QA			KG-Comp			CV-QA		
	Ret	D-Pre	D-Ver	Ret	D-Pre	D-Ver	Ret	D-Pre	D-Ver
Data profiling (DP)	-	-	-	-	-	-	250	1	234
Clustering (CL)	200	3	177	84	26	38	250	0	235
Correlation analysis (CA)	200	7	173	-	-	-	500	0	485
Anomaly detection (AD)	94	1	73	79	25	34	200	1	184
Association rules (AR)	-	-	-	-	-	-	105	0	90
Regression (RE)	200	5	175	200	24	156	392	0	377
Classification (CS)	200	4	176	200	15	165	312	0	297
Forecasting (FC)	200	1	179	200	40	140	200	0	185
Causal inference (CI)	-	-	-	-	-	-	500	0	485

Table 6: Number of retrieved (Ret), discarded in the preprocessing (D-Pre) or in the verification (D-Ver) files

This pipeline produced validation datasets with sufficient quality and balance for subsequent experimentation.

4.1.4 Experimental Evaluation

Two main aspects were studied: (i) the ability of different LLMs to classify analytical intents, and (ii) the impact of dataset source on classification performance.

- **Datasets:** KG-QA, KG-Comp, and CV-QA (Table 5) were used, each representing different types of problem descriptions.
- **LLMs:** Both open-source models (Mistral, Mixtral, Llama 3) and proprietary ones (GPT-3.5-turbo, GPT-4) were evaluated.

Results (Table 7) confirm that GPT-4 achieves the highest accuracy, followed by Llama 3-70B. Notably, Llama 3-70B outperforms GPT-3.5 despite its smaller size. In contrast, Mixtral-8x22B produced inconsistent outputs, underperforming compared to smaller models.

Across datasets, KG-QA yielded the best results, while KG-Comp and CV-QA showed similar performance. The lower accuracy compared to the dataset of [4] can be attributed to the noisier, more realistic nature of user-generated content. The analysis also highlights the impact of dataset characteristics: KG-QA benefited from more diverse natural language questions, whereas CV-QA suffered from high noise levels and fewer classes (Table 8)

Classifier	KG-QA	KG-Comp	CV-QA	Average
GPT-4	0.93	0.86	0.88	0.89
GPT-3.5 Turbo	0.91	0.78	0.79	0.82
Mixtral-8x22b-instruct	0.68	0.66	0.75	0.69
Mixtral-8x7b-instruct	0.8	0.89	0.73	0.80
Mistral-7b-instruct	0.78	0.76	0.61	0.71
Llama3-70b	0.93	0.82	0.85	0.86
Llama3-8b	0.74	0.65	0.61	0.66

Table 7: Accuracy on expanded validation sets

Dataset	Precision									Recall								
	DP	CL	CA	AD	AR	CS	RE	FC	CI	DP	CL	CA	AD	AR	CS	RE	FC	CI
KG-QA	–	1.00	1.00	0.95	–	0.85	0.94	0.82	–	–	1.00	1.00	1.00	–	0.85	0.80	0.90	–
KG-Comp	–	1.00	–	1.00	–	0.70	1.00	0.77	–	–	0.75	–	0.85	–	0.95	0.75	1.00	–
CV-QA	1.00	0.93	0.88	0.83	1.00	0.83	0.83	0.79	0.93	0.53	0.93	0.93	1.00	0.93	1.00	0.67	1.00	0.93

Table 8: Precision and recall for each intent class with GPT-4

4.2 Automatic Capturing and Classification of Constraints

This subsection focuses on the formalisation and classification of user-defined constraints in the context of ML and AutoML processes. Constraints represent an essential element of intent anticipation, as they specify conditions, requirements, or limitations that shape the execution of analytical workflows. The work presented here introduces an extended Knowledge Graph (KG) model for constraint representation, a taxonomy to structure the space of possible constraints, and a methodology for capturing them automatically from natural language.

4.2.1 Knowledge Graph Extension

The first step was to extend the KG schema to semantically annotate triples extracted from user-defined ML constraints. The KG serves as the backbone for storing constraints in a structured, queryable form and provides the semantic continuity required to integrate constraint information into downstream components, including retrieval and reasoning via SPARQL-based querying.

The KG design was informed by prior work in the ExtremeXP project, which developed a representation for AutoML workflows, algorithmic components (via DMOP [9]), and user metadata. However, the original schema only partially addressed constraints, providing limited support for their explicit representation. In particular, it lacked mechanisms for handling negative constraints (e.g., “do not evaluate using a confusion matrix”), did not clearly distinguish between requirements and constraints, and failed to link parameters (e.g., *seed* = 1234) to their associated algorithms in a semantically robust way. For an example see Figure 23.

To overcome these limitations, we revised the “Const/Req” portion of the knowledge graph backbone (see Figure 1). The redesigned structure improves expressivity and precision, standardises terminology, and integrates constraints seamlessly with existing conceptual nodes (e.g., *Algorithm/Process*). This ensures continuity with the original KG while enabling a richer and more

interpretable representation of ML constraints. Ultimately, this enhanced KG improves the ability of LLMs to generate accurate triples and populate the graph.

Figure 23: Example applied on the ExtremeXP KG backbone

4.2.2 Constraints Taxonomy

A prerequisite for extending the ontology was the definition of a taxonomy that captures the full range of constraints users may impose in AutoML workflows. The taxonomy provides multiple benefits:

- **Functional:** it directs each extracted constraint to the appropriate execution path.
- **Semantic:** it ensures standardised and consistent representation of related concepts.
- **Ontological:** it organises concepts hierarchically, supporting inheritance, reasoning, and improved graph navigation.

The taxonomy is structured around a modular decomposition of AutoML into phases, components, and methods, collectively referred to as *Characteristics*. It draws on established AutoML libraries, academic literature [7], and practical toolkits. Four top-level categories were identified (**Error! Reference source not found.**):

- **Preprocessing:** operations such as data cleaning (duplicate removal, handling missing values), transformation (normalisation, encoding, dimensionality reduction), feature engineering, and outlier detection [10].
- **Combined Algorithm Selection and Hyperparameter optimisation (CASH):** supervised and unsupervised algorithm choices (e.g., logistic regression, random forests, SVMs, k-means, Gaussian mixtures) together with hyperparameter configurations [6].
- **Execution Configuration:** parameters that constrain pipeline behaviour, such as maximum runtime, observation weights, maximum number of models, and leaderboard criteria [8].
- **Data Visualization:** supportive techniques for interpretability and analysis, including bar charts, scatter plots, histograms, and box plots.

By organising ML processes in this structured way, the taxonomy provides both a comprehensive coverage of potential constraints and a semantically consistent basis for ontology-driven modelling.

Figure 24: Taxonomy of AutoML constraints

4.2.3 Integration with Intent Capturing

Building on the results of Section 4.1, the taxonomy and KG extension enable constraints to be captured from natural language input using LLM-based extraction. This integration allows user-specified constraints to be transformed into RDF triples (as it will be discussed in the next section), classified under the taxonomy, and stored in the KG. As a result, user profiles can combine both analytical intents and the constraints that condition their execution, significantly enhancing the predictive modelling of user behaviour in analytical contexts.

4.3 Mapping Intents and Constraints to Knowledge Graph Concepts

This subsection presents the process of mapping the analytical intents and user constraints captured in Sections 4.1 and 4.2 onto the structured representation of the KG. The objective of this task is to ensure that user-provided inputs, expressed in natural language, are grounded in a consistent semantic framework that supports reasoning, disambiguation, and integration with downstream modules. By linking intents and constraints to KG concepts, we transform unstructured user expressions into interpretable entities that can be automatically processed, queried, and related to one another.

4.3.1 Motivation and Problem Statement

Although the taxonomies for intents and constraints provide a controlled vocabulary for capturing user behaviour, natural language expressions are often ambiguous and imprecise. For instance, a user might request to “evaluate the model with accuracy” without specifying the evaluation method or may refer to “forest” without clarifying that a Random Forest classifier is intended. Similarly, constraints such as “do not use a confusion matrix” require both the recognition of a negative statement and its proper alignment with an evaluation metric in the KG. Without mapping to KG concepts, such instructions would remain unstructured, leading to inconsistencies and hindering interoperability across the broader Task 4.4 pipeline.

The mapping step addresses these issues by providing a systematic method for linking captured intents and constraints to well-defined KG entities. This ensures unambiguous interpretation, enables semantic continuity, and allows for advanced reasoning — such as inferring relationships between constraints, detecting contradictions, or recommending alternatives.

4.3.2 Overview

The task of associating or mapping textual mentions in a document with their corresponding entities in a KG is known as Entity Linking (EL), a fundamental step in transforming unstructured text into

structured knowledge. EL is commonly implemented as a three-stage pipeline: Mention Detection, which identifies text spans that may correspond to entities; Candidate Generation, which retrieves the top-k possible entities from a KG (often based on entity-mention statistics); and Entity Disambiguation (ED), which selects the final entity from the candidate set.

Traditionally, ED has relied on task-specific models trained on large corpora such as Wikipedia [14]. More recent approaches exploit contextual information [27, 19, 16], or enrich candidate representations with descriptions [29] and classes [31], enabling zero-shot ED where unseen entities can be recognized.

The advent of LLMs such as GPT-3 [17], GPT-4 [12], or LLaMA-2 [38] has further advanced ED, as these models capture broad world knowledge and perform well in zero-shot settings [42]. However, LLMs also face limitations, including hallucinations [26] and incomplete knowledge. To address this, KGs—whether encyclopedic (e.g., DBpedia [13], YAGO [36]), commonsense (e.g., ConceptNet [35]), or domain-specific [11]—can be used to guide inference. This line of work, known as KG-enhanced LLM inference [32], leverages structured KG information during inference rather than retraining [25, 40, 15, 37].

In our approach, KG information is integrated into ED to improve zero-shot performance. Instead of asking the LLM to freely choose an entity from a candidate set, we extract the candidates’ class taxonomy from the KG and use it to constrain disambiguation. For example, in Figure 25 (Query 1), given the mention “MTV awards”, the entity *Justin* is more likely a *Musician* than a *Politician*, which rules out *Justin Trudeau*. When remaining candidates share the same class, we further retrieve candidate descriptions from a knowledge base (e.g., Wikipedia) and include them in the prompt (Figure 25, Query 2). This Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) [28] stage reduces hallucination and enables robust predictions even for entities unseen during LLM training.

Figure 25: Overview of the two steps of our approach

4.3.3 Proposed method: ED with KG-enhanced LLMs

In this section we formulate the problem and describe the two main steps of the proposed method.

4.3.3.1 Problem Formulation

Let $C = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_{|C|}\}$ be a set of k candidate entities from a KG with a class hierarchy, and m be a mention in document/text input d . The goal of ED is to assign to m the correct entity $e \in C$.

4.3.3.2 Method

Our approach consists of two steps: subgraph generation and a pruning algorithm. First, a subgraph is built with the candidates and their taxonomy of classes. Then, pruning iteratively removes candidates until only one remains, which is taken as the solution (Figure 25).

Subgraph Generation. Given the candidate set C , a directed acyclic graph (DAG) G is created from the KG, with *Thing* as the root and the candidates as leaves. Since entities can belong to multiple classes (e.g., *Justin Timberlake* is both *Musician* and *Actor*), G is not necessarily a tree.

The construction proceeds in four steps (Figure 26): (1) candidates are linked to their classes; (2) classes not serving as predecessors are removed; (3) redundant and self-pointing relations are discarded; and (4) intermediate nodes with only one non-entity successor are collapsed to improve granularity. For example, in DBpedia the path *Thing* → *Species* → *Eukaryote* → *Person* → *Artist* → *Musician* is reduced to more informative nodes. In complex KGs like YAGO, entities can also serve as classes; in these cases, an extra preprocessing step ensures they remain as leaves.

Figure 26: Overview of the steps for simplifying candidate subgraphs into a DAG for pruning

Pruning Algorithm. The pruning algorithm (Algorithm 1) starts from the generated graph G and iteratively narrows down candidates using the Lowest Common Ancestor (LCA), defined as the deepest node that is an ancestor of all candidates (Figure 27, dashed nodes). Depending on the LCA's direct successors, three cases arise:

1. All successors are classes (Figure 27, case 1). The LLM is prompted to decide which classes fit the mention m . Non-selected classes and their disconnected subgraphs are removed (Algorithm 1, lines 5–12).
2. All successors are entities (Figure 27, case 2). The LLM is prompted to select the correct entity. Candidate descriptions are retrieved from a KB and appended to the prompt. Non-selected entities are removed (Algorithm 1, lines 13–15).
3. Mixed classes and entities (Figure 27, case 3). Successors are split into classes (D_c) and entities (D_e). The LLM selects from $D_c' = D_c \cup \{Other\}$, where *Other* is an additional class which

encompasses D_e . If the LLM selects a class belonging to D_c , the remaining classes and the entities D_e are removed from G . If *Other* is selected, the classes from D_c are removed. Finally, the nodes which have become disconnected from the root are also removed (Algorithm 1, lines 16-22).

Figure 27: Example of the three different configurations of the LCA's direct successors

Input: Subgraph G , mention m , document d and entity *descriptions*
Output: Entity

```

1 candidates  $\leftarrow$  leaves( $G$ );
2 while len(candidates)  $\neq$  1 do
3   LCA  $\leftarrow$  LCA( $G$ , candidates);
4   directSuccessors  $\leftarrow$  directSuccessors( $G$ , LCA);
5   if allDirSuccessorsAreClasses then
6     response  $\leftarrow$  multiChoice(directSuccessors  $\cup$  {None},  $m$ ,  $d$ );
7     if response  $\neq$  None then
8        $G$   $\leftarrow$  prune( $G$ , directSuccessors  $\setminus$  {response});
9     else
10      response  $\leftarrow$  multiChoice(candidates,  $m$ ,  $d$ , descriptions);
11       $G$   $\leftarrow$  prune( $G$ , candidates  $\setminus$  {response});
12  else if allDirSuccessorsAreEntities then
13    response  $\leftarrow$  multiChoice(directSuccessors,  $m$ ,  $d$ , descriptions);
14     $G$   $\leftarrow$  prune( $G$ , directSuccessors  $\setminus$  {response});
15  else
16     $D_c, D_e$   $\leftarrow$  getClassesAndEntities(directSuccessors);
17    response  $\leftarrow$  multiChoice( $D_c$   $\cup$  {Other},  $m$ ,  $d$ );
18    if response = Other then
19       $G$   $\leftarrow$  prune( $G$ ,  $D_c$ );
20    else
21       $G$   $\leftarrow$  prune( $G$ , directSuccessors  $\setminus$  {response});
22 candidates  $\leftarrow$  leaves( $G$ );

```

Algorithm 1: Pruning candidates

To improve robustness, two safeguards are added: (i) in case 1, a *None* class allows the LLM to skip to case 2 if no class matches; and (ii) whenever a single entity remains after case 1 or 3, the LLM is asked to confirm it before accepting the result, otherwise a full case 2 prompt is triggered.

The algorithm runs until only one leaf (entity) remains in G , which is returned as the final response. In the worst case, the LLM is prompted k times (i.e., candidate entities from a KG).

4.3.4 Experimental evaluation

We now present the experimental evaluation. First, we describe the settings, datasets, and models used. Then, we compare our approach against different methods and analyze the effect of the KG. Since no domain-specific datasets exist for analytical intents and constraints, we rely on established ED benchmarks, thereby validating the methodology in a general setting. Finally, we examine scenarios where the method fails to disambiguate correctly.

4.3.4.1 Settings and Datasets

Datasets. We evaluate the approach on ten widely used ED datasets, the same as in [20]. These include news and online articles (MSN [18], AQU [30], ACE04 [33], CWEB [21], R128 [34], R500 [34]), Wikipedia-based sets (WIKI [15], OKE15 [30], OKE16 [31]), and hand-crafted ambiguous sentences (KORE [24]). Each dataset provides documents with annotated mentions linked to their ground truth entities. Statistics are reported in Table 9.

Candidate Sets. For comparability, we use the candidate sets from [20], with size 10. They are built using Wikipedia hyperlink count statistics [27, 19, 14], and, when insufficient, extended via BLINK [41], a dense retrieval model leveraging context and entity descriptions.

Knowledge Graphs. YAGO [36] is used to derive class hierarchies. It integrates schema.org [22] and Wikidata [39] taxonomies with Wikipedia infobox data. To study the role of granularity we also use DBpedia [13], whose ontology is shallower and manually curated. For entity descriptions, we rely on Wikipedia, truncated at 250 characters before being appended to prompts.

Evaluation Metric. Results are reported using inKB micro-F1 (Equation 1), where inKB means the ground truth entity must exist in the KG. To compare across KGs with different entity coverage, we also compute the percentage of the Gold F1 score, i.e., the maximum possible inKB micro-F1 given candidate sets. Weighted averages across datasets are reported to account for size differences.

$$\text{micro} - F1 = TP / (TP + 1/2(FP + FN)) \quad (1)$$

Large Language Models. Experiments use GPT-3.5 (gpt-3.5-turbo-1106 via the OpenAI API), with temperature set to 0 to reduce randomness and encourage factual answers. This choice balances reasoning capability, cost, and availability.

	# Docs	# Mentions	Avg. # Characters
KORE	50	144	76.4
ACE04	35	257	2285.0
OKE16	173	288	186.2
R500	357	524	164.8
OKE15	101	536	183.9
R128	113	650	818.8
MSN	20	656	3380.1
AQU	50	727	1415.9
WIKI	319	6793	1624.6
CWEB	320	11154	7575.9

Table 9: Overview of ten considered datasets' statistics

4.3.4.2 Results

We compare our method against (i) a non-enhanced LLM baseline, (ii) ChatEL [20] — a zero-shot LLM prompting approach — and (iii) ReFinED [14], a task-specific ED model trained on large Wikipedia data.

- **Baseline:** the LLM is asked to pick directly from the candidate set (no class or description enrichment).
- **ChatEL:** runs two LLM prompts (describe mention, then match to candidates enriched with Wikipedia descriptions). Note ChatEL may return empty responses when the LLM outputs no candidate; we account for this by using the *Gold F1* percentage to make scores comparable.
- **ReFinED:** RoBERTa-based, pretrained on $\approx 100M$ mention-entity pairs and fine-tuned on AIDA-CoNLL.

Table 10 summarises results. Our method outperforms the baseline on every dataset, showing that KG guidance and prompt design improve disambiguation beyond what a plain LLM yields (e.g., baseline mistakes include over-reliance on context: “*Phoenix*” linked to *Phoenix Suns* instead of the place). Compared with ChatEL, our approach is better on 6/10 datasets (weighted average +1.8 percentage points), despite using GPT-3.5 rather than GPT-4 (ChatEL’s GPT-4 runs are costlier). Graph preprocessing (LCA/pruning) adds negligible overhead: graph ops are \sim two orders of magnitude faster than LLM calls.

Compared to ReFinED, the specialised model outperforms ours on 6 datasets (weighted avg +1.5 pp), which is expected given its massive training; however, on the out-of-domain KORE set our approach surpasses ReFinED by >25 pp, highlighting LLM methods’ adaptability without task-specific training.

	KORE	ACE04	OKE16	R500	OKE15	R128	MSN	AQU	WIKI	CWEB	Avg.	Wt. avg.
<i>Baseline</i>	F1-Score	68.2	89.1	59.0	77.4	68.7	82.3	62.4	69.5	65.0		
	Gold F1	76.5	95.4	82.2	85.3	83.6	94.0	96.2	89.4	89.3		
	% Gold	89.3	93.4	71.7	90.8	82.1	87.5	64.8	77.7	72.8	80.8	75.4
<i>ReFinED</i> [14]	F1-Score	56.7	86.4	79.4	70.8	68.0	89.1	86.1	84.1	73.8		
	Gold F1	88.0	96.9	90.3	92.1	91.1	97.0	98.1	94.4	94.3		
	% Gold	64.4	89.1	87.9	76.8	74.6	91.8	87.7	89.0	78.2	82.8	82.6
<i>ChatEL</i> [20]	F1-Score	78.7	89.3	75.2	82.2	78.9	88.1	76.7	79.1	70.9		
	Gold F1	88.0	96.9	90.3	92.1	91.1	97.0	98.1	94.4	94.3		
	% Gold	89.4	92.1	83.2	89.2	86.6	90.8	78.1	83.7	75.1	85.2	79.3
<i>OurDpedita</i>	F1-Score	71.3	89.4	65.9	75.4	75.0	84.2	72.0	72.5	67.7		
	Gold F1	80.1	95.7	79.8	85.6	85.9	94.1	96.3	90.4	89.4		
	% Gold	88.9	93.3	82.5	88.0	89.3	87.3	89.4	80.2	75.7	85.0	78.8
<i>OurYAGO</i>	F1-Score	71.8	88.7	65.8	78.3	75.8	81.2	72.0	74.4	69.6		
	Gold F1	79.6	94.3	83.7	85.2	84.8	92.2	94.4	88.9	89.3		
	% Gold	90.1	94.0	78.6	91.9	85.4	89.4	88.0	76.2	83.6	85.5	81.1

Table 10: Results for the inKB micro F1-score for the ED experiments with ten datasets.

The ChatEL and ReFinED scores are taken from the results reported by the authors in [20]. The weighted average weights each score by taking into consideration the sizes of the datasets. The best score for each dataset is highlighted in **bold**

4.3.4.3 *KG Expressivity Impact*

We evaluated the effect of taxonomy granularity by comparing **YAGO** and **DBpedia** (Table 11). YAGO has far more classes and greater depth (see Figure 28), offering richer semantic distinctions (e.g., *Barcelona* as *Place* vs *Organization* in YAGO, only *Place* in DBpedia). Repeating the experiments (same settings) shows YAGO outperforms DBpedia in 7/10 datasets (weighted avg +2.4 pp), supporting the hypothesis that a more expressive class taxonomy aids disambiguation.

	DBpedia	YAGO
# Instances	5,044,223	6,349,359
# Classes	760	819,292
Avg. tree depth	3.51	6.61
Avg. branching factor	4.53	8.48

Table 11: Metric comparisons from YAGO and DBpedia KGs [23]

Figure 28: Class representation of the entity *Barcelona* in DBpedia (left) and YAGO (right) KGs

Iteration counts are similar for both KGs (mean ≈ 2.2 , Table 12), since preprocessing collapses intermediary nodes. Given graph operations are much cheaper than LLM calls, using deeper graphs does not substantially increase runtime.

	Iterations						Avg. Iterations
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
YAGO	26.24%	37.36%	26.60%	8.30%	1.32%	0.15%	2.21
DBpedia	23.57%	43.00%	26.68%	6.12%	0.42%	0.01%	2.18

Table 12: Percentage of disambiguated entities in which the pruning algorithm reached a final single entity within the specified number of iterations

4.3.4.4 Error Analysis

We categorised failure cases to understand limitations:

- **Ground-truth errors:** incorrect dataset annotations (e.g., *English* annotated as *England*).
- **KG errors:** wrong or missing class annotations (e.g., *Bounty (chocolate bar)* mislabelled as *Architectural Structure*), or inconsistent labelling across related entities.
- **Ambiguous cases:** inherently unclear mentions (e.g., *Justin* in “...popular both on MTV and Twitter” could be Timberlake or Bieber). Some ground-truth labels are debatable (e.g., *principal vs head teacher*).
- **LLM errors:** mistakes from missed context or misinterpretation (e.g., “*Tiger lost the US Open*” – LLM misses that *Tiger* → *Tiger Woods*; other cases reflect wrong class interpretation).

Table 13 classifies errors from the smaller KORE and ACE2004 datasets. Examples include one annotation error (ground truth), two KG missing-class errors and one wrong entity label (KG errors), five ambiguous cases, and 12 LLM errors (5 due to missed context, 7 due to wrong class interpretation). A small follow-up with stronger models (GPT-4 and Mistral Large) corrected 8 and 7 of those 12 LLM errors respectively, indicating that more capable LLMs can mitigate a portion of the remaining failures.

Error Type	# Errors
LLM error	12
Ambiguous error	5
KG error	3
Ground truth error	1

Table 13: Error types for the ACE2004 and KORE datasets, using YAGO as the KG

4.4 Intent Recommendation via Knowledge Graph Embeddings

The KG presented in Task 4.3 was designed to annotate the end-to-end interaction between a user and the workflows generated within a Data Assistant (DA). When a user requests a ML task, the inputs, the generated workflow, and the feedback are automatically annotated. This data enables the system to produce new recommendations for subsequent requests by the same or other users. Initially, however, the KG suffers from the cold start problem, as no data exists until the system is in operation. To mitigate this, data about the components of ML workflows, along with workflows themselves, has been obtained and annotated.

4.4.1 Data Instantiation

To create instances for DA elements (e.g., algorithms, datasets, hyperparameters), several resources were used. DMOP's DMKB [45] provides algorithm annotations linked to their classes and properties. For example, Logistic Regression is instantiated as a Discriminative Algorithm with specific features (e.g., assumptions, optimization strategy) and properties such as *EagerPolicyLearning*. All DMKB algorithms were linked to their intent at the ML Task level (Figure 2). As DMKB is incomplete, additional algorithms were instantiated, linking them to their intent, algorithm class, and hyperparameters. Since workflow generators rely on scikit-learn [46], its components were instantiated in the KG.

Datasets were drawn from OpenML (68 for classification) [47] and UCI (28 for regression) [48]. Relevant characteristics were automatically extracted and annotated (Table 14).

	Categorical	Numerical
# of Instances	✓	✓
# of Features	✓	✓
# of Numeric Features	✓	✓
# of Categorical Features	✓	✓
% of Missing Values	✓	✓
# of Classes in Target	✓	
Target Imbalance	✓	
StD Target		✓
Target Type	✓	✓

Table 14: Example of features extracted from the datasets, depending on the target variable

4.4.2 Workflow Annotation

Workflows ideally come from real DA Assistant interactions, but as no such dataset exists, they were emulated. The KG was populated with workflows optimized by AutoML tools HyperOpt-Sklearn [44] and TPOT [43], applied to the datasets above. These tools optimize pipelines using scikit-learn algorithms and hyperparameters with search strategies like Tree of Parzen Estimators and Genetic Programming. Each workflow—consisting of preprocessing steps and a prediction algorithm—was annotated following the schema in Figure 1. Constraints (e.g., template *Selector + Classifier*) could be captured as in Figure 29. Although these AutoML tools cover only part of the KG's expressivity, they were not extended since workflow generator design is out of scope.

Figure 29: Instantiation of a template constraint

4.4.3 Recommending/Anticipating User Intents

The KG captures complete analytics workflows, enabling user assistance during workflow creation. Recommendations for user inputs are produced, e.g., suggesting potential analyses for a dataset. User inputs depend on objectives and may not have a unique “correct” answer. For example, a regression dataset could be treated as classification if the response variable is discretized. The aim is to provide sensible, optional suggestions.

4.4.3.1 Basic Approach

A first method exploited predefined SPARQL queries on the KG. These queries leverage past interactions from the same or different users and are interpretable, domain-expert-driven, and easily updated without retraining. For instance, for a user requesting a classification workflow with the Iris dataset, the system may suggest an evaluation metric by running progressively more general queries. To illustrate the approach, let’s think of a user who requests a workflow for the Iris dataset and their intent is classification. Then, the system could suggest the metric for which the workflow generation should be optimized. To answer it, the system starts by running a very specific query, and it keeps increasing the level of generalization until an answer is returned. For instance, the system could run Query 1: *Which is the most frequent metric the user has specified in the past with the Iris dataset for a Classification task?* However, the user may not have used the Iris dataset before, hence another query could be used to allow more generalization: Query 2: *Which is the most frequent metric the user has specified in the past for Classification tasks?* Yet, it may be the first time the user interacts with the system, hence different queries must be run in this case. Query 3: *Which is the most frequent metric used with the Iris dataset for a Classification task by all the users?* in case the Iris dataset has been used before, or Query 4: *Which is the most frequent metric used in Classification tasks by all users?* when the Iris dataset has not been used. These queries can be further restricted with different filters, such as the domain of the analysis or the size of the dataset. In Figure 30, a SPARQL example of Query 4 filtered by the users’ level of expertise is shown.

QUERY

```
SELECT ?metric (COUNT(?metric) AS ?Counts) WHERE {
  ?user intOnt:runs ?workflow.
  ?user person:hasExpertise intOnt:Beginner.
  ?workflow intOnt:hasTask ?task.
  ?task intOnt:hasIntent intOnt:Classification.
  ?task intOnt:hasRequirement ?evaluation.
  ?evaluation intOnt:onMetric ?Metric}
GROUP BY (?metric) ORDER BY DESC(?Counts) LIMIT 3
```

Results
Accuracy
F1-Score
Precision

Figure 30: Example of an SPARQL query over the KG

While effective, this approach requires predefining query orders and can become complex and inflexible when broader KG information is needed.

4.4.3.2 *Exploiting the Graph’s Structure*

Beyond queries, KGs can be analyzed with ML techniques. To reduce computational cost and allow ML integration, KG elements can be transformed into low-dimensional feature vectors, i.e., knowledge graph embeddings (KGEs).

4.4.3.3 *Knowledge Graph Embeddings*

KGEs represent entities and relations as vectors while preserving graph semantics. Techniques include translational models like TransE, TransH, TransR, RotatE [49, 50, 51, 52] (Figure 31), bilinear models such as DistMult and ComplEx [53, 54], and neural approaches like ConvKB [55]. These embeddings support recommender systems (RSs), which naturally benefit from KGs [56, 57] by capturing user–item interactions and properties. KGEs enrich representations, capture context, and mitigate cold start, as new entities (e.g., an algorithm linked to DMOP classes) inherit proximity to existing embeddings.

Figure 31: Simplified 2D visualization of the intuition behind the different translational embedding models

For instance, a new algorithm will have an associated Intent and will be linked to some algorithm classes and characteristics from DMOP, which will be shared with other algorithms already present in the KG. Therefore, these algorithms will be close in the embedding space, which can be leveraged for the generation of recommendations.

However, the anticipation needs for the user intentions modelled in this work have multiple interactions to be recommended, resulting in different objects acting as users or as items, which in turn evolve while the user’s input is being extended. To exemplify the problem, we could think about a user who starts requesting a workflow. First of all, the system could suggest to them the dataset to be used. This first interaction can be clearly recommended, following the terminology presented above, with a user:User and item:Dataset RS. Once the dataset is fixed, the system should provide anticipations for the Intent. There, if a similar RS was to be used (user:User, item:Intent), the information of the selected Dataset would be lost. Hence, a RS with user:(User+Dataset) and item:Intent should be used instead. The problem gets worse once the number of inputs increases or if the difference in the order of the inputs (e.g., the user could select first the Intent and expect the system to provide appropriate datasets) is considered, making the use of simple RS not feasible.

4.4.3.4 Link Prediction

To overcome this difficulty, the Link Prediction (LP) method has been explored to act as a RS. LP is a technique that can be applied over KGs [58, 59] in order to find missing or future relations between entities. Therefore, given that the users’ inputs have been captured in the designed schema (i.e., all the relations needed for the anticipation task are present in the KG), the KG structure can be exploited with the LP task to provide suggestions. This procedure can be done with different methods, such as measuring similarity between entities or by using the graph topology (e.g., Common Neighbours). KGE can be used to predict these missing links as well, by using the model trained for the embeddings. For instance, if the model is trained to minimize translation distance by addition like in TransE (i.e., $h + r \approx t$, see Figure 31), we can look for the entities whose tail embeddings are closer to the summation of the head and relation embeddings. Thus, this technique gives flexibility to the recommendation engine, as it does neither lock the input nor the output of the recommendation. The relations that can be used to anticipate the user’s input (i.e., the elements that define the task the workflow aims to solve) are highlighted in Figure 32. The general intention of the requested workflow is captured by hasIntent, hasRequirement captures the evaluation protocol and hasConstraint links the workflow with the different constraints the user may pose.

Figure 32: Overview of classes and properties relevant for the anticipation task

4.4.4 Experimental Evaluation

In this section, different experiments of the application of KGEs and LP to the designed KG have been performed, having two main goals. On the one hand, they aim to evaluate the KGEs’ ability to capture the whole KG, by comparing different embedding models and parameter configurations. On the other

hand, they assess to which extent the LP task can be used to provide sensible recommendations in the studied domain.

4.4.4.1 Methodology

The experiments have been created following the general methodology presented in [60], which focuses on good practices in the experiment design for computer systems.

Goals and Systems

The experiments have been conducted to evaluate the performance of different KGEs in order to determine their ability to capture the KG and to potentially be effective for the general LP task. While doing so, the influence of the different parameters on the performance has been studied.

Services and Outcomes

To produce the experiments, the PyKeen [61] Python library has been used. This library enables the creation of reproducible KGEs experiments, with multiple functionalities, tuning parameters, and models. With that, from a set of triples, KGEs have been learned in a training phase and assessed over a validation set in the evaluation stage.

Metrics

As in most ML tasks, in KGE a loss function is optimized in the training phase to obtain the most suitable embeddings. When KGEs are learned for LP, one of the most usual loss functions is the Margin Ranking Loss (MRL):

$$MRL = \sum_{(h_i, r_i, t_i)} \max(0, m + f(h_i^+, r_i, t_i) - f(h_i^-, r_i, t_i))$$

The objective of this loss function is to give a better score to positive triples (i.e., those that exist in the dataset) than to the negative ones (i.e., those which are synthetically generated by corrupting some of the entities of the positive triple [62]), emulating the LP task. When the difference between the score of the two entities is larger than the specified margin (m), no loss is accounted for. The score function f depends on the given embedding model.

For instance, for TransE, which is a simple embedding technique that sees the translation as the addition of the head and relation embeddings, the scoring function is the q -norm of the mismatch of the translation in the embedding space:

$$f(h, r, t) = -\|e_h + e_r - e_t\|_q$$

During the evaluation phase, the head ($?$, r , t) and the tail (h , r , $?$) are removed from the triple of the test set, and LP is performed on both incomplete triples.

The Hits@ k metric is usually used to assess the evaluation, as it measures the proportion of times the correct result (i.e., the entity missing for the LP) is shown among the top- k ranked entities. Therefore, it replicates the case of showing only a few highly ranked items to users in recommendation engines. Moreover, given the expected usage of the LP task (i.e., present the users some suggestions), the evaluation metric that has been given more relevance is Hits@3. This is because using three suggestions presents the users a sufficient number of choices while not overwhelming them with excessive options.

Parameters

The main parameters that can affect the generation of the embeddings are:

- **Models:** Different proposed models capture the head and tail relationship based on different principles and assumptions. Hence, the performance on the LP task can be widely influenced by the model choice.
- **Embedding Dimension:** This is the dimension of the vector space in which the entities are represented. In general, the larger the dimension, the more hidden relationships that can be captured by the model. However, increasing the dimension can lead to overfitting on the training data (and thus poorer performance over unseen triples) and computational complexity problems. Therefore, a wide range of values will be explored to find a trade-off between the complexity of the hidden relationships captured and generalization.
- **Learning Rate:** The learning rate is an important hyperparameter in the training of various ML algorithms, as it determines the step size at which the model updates its parameters during the training process. It can have a significant impact on the performance of the model, as a high learning rate could cause the model to overshoot the optimal solution, leading to unstable behaviour, or, on the other hand, a low learning rate could result in slow convergence or the model getting stuck in a local minimum.
- **Number of negative samples per positive sample (NPP):** Previous studies [63] indicate that increasing its value may improve the evaluation metric, albeit at the cost of greater computational complexity. This is because by increasing the NPP the model learns to discriminate better the negative samples, thus generating less False Positives in the inference phase. However, increasing the value too much could hinder the model's ability to detect positive instances, which greatly affects the LP task.
- **Negative Samples Generator:** Different negative samples generators can be used (e.g., Uniform Sampler, Bernoulli Sampler, etc.), which can influence the results by creating training samples of different quality.
- **Number of Epochs:** The number of epochs of the experiments can also affect the results. For instance, a low number of epochs can lead to underfitting, as the model has not had enough time to learn about the data, but a large number of them could lead to overfitting if the model is able to memorize the training data and lose generalization.

Factors to Study

In the experiments, the variables that have been studied are:

- **Models:** Popular translational (i.e., TransH, TransE, TransR, RotatE) and bilinear models (i.e., DistMult, ComplEx) have been studied.
- **Embedding Dimension:** The values tested range from 2 to 256, in the powers of two, as it is a usual rule-of-thumb in structure sizes when GPUs are used. In all our experiments the performance of the model stabilizes with embedding sizes within the proposed range.
- **Learning Rate:** The range of values explored starts at 0.1, and then exponentially lower values (e.g., 0.01, 0.001) have been assessed.
- **NPP:** The explored range has been between 1 (the usual default value) and 100.

The remaining two variables (i.e., *Negative Samples Generator and Number of Epochs*) have not been studied as they have been fixed in advance. First of all, for the *Negative Samples Generator*, the Bernoulli generator has been used instead of the Uniform one, as it generates higher quality corrupted triples for the training phase by selecting the best entity (i.e., tail or head) to change. Regarding the *Number of Epochs*, although in the experimental set up Early Stopping has been enabled, the maximum value has been fixed to 300, which has not been reached by any experiment.

Evaluation Techniques

As previously mentioned, the PyKEEN library has been used to generate and evaluate the experiments. The different combinations of models and hyperparameters have first been tested in a grid search approach. To perform the experiments, the data has been split in three sets (i.e., train, test, and validation) in a stratified manner. This is, they have been split taking into account that, in order to perform the test and validation phases, the entities and relationships appearing in their respective sets must have been first embedded in the training phase. To be more specific, the different sets which have been used for each task are:

- *Training Set*: This is the dataset partition that is used for learning the embeddings. The different models with the specified hyperparameter configuration are trained with this set by minimizing the MRL function. It is important to note that this loss function can neither be compared between models, as they use different techniques to define distances or errors, nor between parameters (e.g., larger embedding sizes can cause the errors to be higher due to vector dimensionality, or a higher number of negative samples per positive sample causes the summation on the loss function to contain more terms). Hence, the results of the loss of the training phase have only been used to assess the performance in scenarios where all the other variables that influence it are fixed.
- *Validation Set*: To use the correct number of epochs and to decrease the computational burden of the experiments, the embeddings have been trained with Early Stopping using the validation set. In this experimental setup, the maximum number of epochs has been set to 300, the number of epochs between validation steps to 15 and the patience to 2. With this configuration, if for an amount of time equivalent to 10% of the total time allocated for training the model has not improved, the learning is stopped.
- *Test Set*: After the training has finished, the final embeddings are used to evaluate the test partition. With that, the different metrics (e.g., Hits@k, average rank, etc.) are obtained. These results have been used to compare the different models and configurations.

One thing to note is that with the standard LP evaluation, all the entities present in the KG are ranked and used in the Hits@k metrics. Hence, each of the thousands of entities could be presented as a solution, which is not the case of the envisioned anticipation system, which should only suggest plausible entities. This is, the only ranked entities should be those whose class satisfies the range condition of the relation, using the ranking score to disambiguate between them. Moreover, as the users introduce their input in an incremental approach, the search space of recommendations gets gradually constrained as new inputs are fixed. For instance, when recommending algorithm constraints, if a user has already chosen an Intent, the LP engine should only rank the algorithms that satisfy it. Thus, the results obtained in these experiments are pessimistic in terms of the entities suggested.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that although in the evaluation phase each triple (h, r, t) is converted to the incomplete triples $(?, r, t)$ and $(h, r, ?)$, they should have different importance when considering the results, in concordance with how the LP task will be used in the anticipation phase and with the nature of the KG design. To exemplify it, let's think about a user, *User10*, who wants to create a DA workflow over a dataset. If we are interested in anticipating the relation *hasIntent*, the system will request the highest-ranking entities that satisfy the triple $(TaskU10, hasIntent, ?)$, which is one of the incomplete triples generated in the evaluation $(h, t, ?)$. It can be seen that using the other incomplete triple $(?, hasIntent, Classification)$ adds unnecessary difficulty to the evaluation, as there are multiple workflows that could satisfy that, and does not relate to the anticipation capabilities needed.

Dataset

The dataset used for the generation of the embeddings is made of the triples defining the KG’s schema, the triples defining the experiments (both classification and regression), the triples describing the datasets and the auxiliary triples created to instantiate the knowledge base with the scikit-learn concepts used by the workflow generator. This corresponds to more than 20.000 triples, summarized in Table 15, which have been partitioned in the three previously defined sets.

	Number of Triples
KG schema	3252
Meta Features	2822
Scikit-Learn Concepts	1285
Experiments	13262

Table 15: Summary of the number of triples present in each source

4.4.4.2 Experiment

The experiments have been distributed in two phases in order to maximize the information without excessive computational resources. On the first one, all the mentioned models have been evaluated with a not extensive number of configurations, in order to identify the general effects of the parameters on the LP performance. When needed, more concrete experiments have been carried out with a wider range of configurations. After that, the most promising KGE model has been chosen, and it has gone through an automatic fine-tuning step to get a more optimal configuration of parameters.

4.4.4.3 Results

First of all, the general metric used to evaluate the experiments has been Hits@3, due to its resemblance to the recommendation task. Additionally, as explained in previous sections, the embeddings are expected to perform significantly better in the tail predictions than in the head ones. This behaviour has been clearly observed, as the tail to head average performance value is 8.2 for ComplEx, 2.7 for DistMult, 4.3 for RotatE, 8.6 for TransE, 7.7 for TransH and 9.1 for TransR. Hence, unless a different evaluation is stated, the following experiments, which explore the influence of the parameters under study on the evaluation score, have been reported with the tail prediction of the realistic (i.e., giving the average ranking position between the entities that have the same loss) Hits@3 metric.

For the embedding dimension parameter, the expected and previously described behaviour can be seen in Figure 33 (left). The average evaluation performance grows with the embedding dimension size, but it stabilizes (even decreases) for the high values of the dimension (i.e., 128 and 256). This behaviour is represented for a fixed configuration in Figure 33 (right), where except for the RotatE model, the other models reach their best performance when the embedding dimension presents intermediate values (i.e., 32 or 64). It can also be seen that depending on the model, the embeddings are not capable of capturing the information contained in the KG when a small embedding size (i.e., 2) is used, giving an evaluation score close to 0.

Figure 33: Hits@3 score grouped by Embedding Dimension (left) and dependence of Hits@3 score with Embedding Dimension for different models, with fixed LR, 0.001, and NPP 20 (right).

Regarding NPP, a similar behaviour is observed (Figure 34, top-left), where there is a stabilization of evaluation score gain as the NPP increases. Hence, it is clear that for the addressed task, using the standard configuration of 1 NPP is not enough, and it is beneficial to perform longer training sessions. However, it is worth noting that this behaviour does not apply to all models, as it depends on their scoring function [64]. As can be observed in Figure 34, contrary to TransH or ComplEx, which benefit from having more than one NPP, the results in DistMult are not greatly influenced by the NPP. The last parameter is the Learning Rate, whose influence can be easily seen in the evolution of the loss function during the training phase. For that, Early Stopping has been deactivated, so the results can be clearly appreciated (Figure 35, right). For high values of the Learning Rate (i.e., 0.1), the learning stage is not able to converge, and it ends with an oscillating behaviour. For the rest of values, the loss function reaches values close to 0, with a convergence rate which increases with the learning rate, as expected. However, it is interesting to note that in this setting, a lower loss does not translate to better evaluation results. As can be seen in Figure 35 (left), the test score with the lowest Learning Rate (i.e., 0.0001) is close to 0, which is not the case of the other Learning Rate values which obtained a similar loss score in the training phase, and even the experiment with oscillation behaviour presents a better prediction performance. This behaviour indicates that the slow convergence with the lowest Learning Rate can make the model lose generalization and overfit the training data.

Figure 34: Hits@3 score grouped by NPP (top-left) and influence of the NPP parameter on different models

Figure 35: Effect of the learning rate on the evaluation (left) and on the training loss (right) for a fixed model (Complex, Embedding Dimension=32, NPP=20)

Finally, we can compare the global evaluation results for the different models among all the experiments. Figure 36 shows a graphical summary of the Hits@3 performance. It can be seen that the best overall mean performance is obtained by TransH, which is also the model that obtained the highest evaluation score. It is followed by ComplEx and DistMult, which have a similar mean value, and although the former is designed as an improvement to the latter, DistMult has a higher median. The worst performing model is TransE, the simplest one, which for multiple configurations is not able to capture the graph information.

Figure 36: Boxplot summary of the Hits@3 score grouped by Model

With the results of the experiments, an automatic hyperparameter tuning optimization has been carried out to obtain embeddings with a better performance than those found in the previous experiments. The model chosen for this step has been the translational model TransH, as it has generated the best performing model and the highest mean performance. The hyperparameter optimization has been performed using the Tree-Structured Parzen Estimator (TSE) algorithm, which sequentially constructs probability models from which to draw the hyperparameter configuration based on past performances, aiming to explore the promising areas of the search space. As seen in Table 16, after 100 iterations of the hyperparameter tuning optimization for TransH, the resulting embeddings slightly increased the Hits@3 performance (2.03%) in comparison to the maximum value (i.e., 0.5613) obtained via grid search (see Figure 36). Therefore, the best results have been obtained for hyperparameter configurations that are compliant with the results previously found.

	TransH
Embedding Dimension	42
Learning Rate	0.0012
NPP	50
Hits@3	0.5727

Table 16: Hyperparameter optimization final configuration and results

4.4.5 Domain Expert Validation

The LP results over the whole KG have been used to compare different models, to observe how their performance changes with different hyperparameters and to have a general idea of how well the KG has been captured.

Additionally, although there is no data available for an offline evaluation of the recommendations, the suggestions produced by the LP anticipation system have been qualitatively assessed by a ML expert. For that, 3 classification and 3 regression datasets, which the system has not previously seen, have been fed to the LP engine, as if a new user was requesting workflows for them (see Table 17). Then, all the entities have been scored for the different relations to be anticipated. The decision to not filter the entities (i.e., rank all the entities, not only those compatible with the relation) has been made to also assess the capability of the learned KGE to capture the graph structure. Finally, the top three scoring entities have been presented to the expert, who has assessed them in terms of sensibility and relevance according to the dataset for which they have been produced.

Intent. Regarding the Intent, the system anticipated as a first option in all cases the Intent related to the expected analysis, and the second and third recommendations were also of class Intent. This recommendation could also have been done with a heuristic rule inspecting the nature of the target variable, similarly to what can be done with the query anticipation system. Therefore, given that this characteristic is annotated in the graph, it suggests that this relationship is correctly captured by the KGE. However, the expert pointed out that some users could want to, for instance, discretize a numeric target variable during the preprocessing step, which would result in giving an incorrect suggestion if it is only based on the target’s variable type. Therefore, it is clear that this suggestion should not be done solely by taking into account the variable’s type, hence by using KGEs this error can be mitigated as extra information can influence the recommendation.

Evaluation Requirements. Regarding the anticipation of Evaluation Requirements, once again all the top three recommended entities are relevant, as they correspond to instances of class EvaluationRequirements. Additionally, the suggested entities match the Intent (e.g., F1-Score for classification datasets) for all the experiments with the exception of one of the three regression datasets, where the last suggestion is not relevant to the expected Intent. This behaviour can be explained by the fact that the amount of classification datasets is twice the amount of regression datasets present in the experiments and will not be given by the recommendation engine once the candidates are filtered. With respect to the relevance of the other suggestions, the expert pointed out that they are all sensible and valid, and depend on a more concrete evaluation goal (e.g., if the user’s purpose is to reduce the False Positives in a Classification task, the Precision metric may be prioritized).

Constraints. Regarding the anticipation of Constraints, the behaviour is similar to the one of Evaluation Requirements. First of all, all the recommended entities are members of the appropriate class (i.e., Constraint) and the recommendations adjust to the Intent’s expected purpose. The recommended constraints are sensible, as they recommend well known and powerful algorithms, but depend again on the user’s more fine-grained goal. However, the expert pointed out that for one dataset the constraint NoPreprocessing was suggested, which is usually not advised to constrain

unless there is a strict requirement for it. The reason for this recommendation is that during the automatic creation of workflows to populate the KG, the option of not using a preprocessing step appears frequently, as the synthetic user selected the constraints without any restriction.

Overall, the experiments show that the learned KGEs are a promising solution for capturing the KG, and that by using the LP method, relevant suggestions can be presented to the user.

Dataset	Variables	Instances	Expected Analysis	Intent	Metric	Constraints
Seeds	7	211	Classification	Classification	F1-Score	SVC
				Regression	Accuracy	KNeighborsClassifier
				Clustering	AUC	LogisticRegression
Cancer	29	569	Classification	Classification	Precision	RandomForest
				Regression	Accuracy	SVC
				Clustering	F1-Score	NoPreprocessing
Iris	4	150	Classification	Classification	Accuracy	SVC
				Regression	F1-Score	LogisticRegression
				Clustering	Precision	RandomForest
Boston	14	506	Regression	Regression	R2	SVR
				Classification	MSE	SGDRegressor
				Clustering	RMSE	KNeighborsRegressor
MPG	7	398	Regression	Regression	RMSE	SVR
				Classification	R2	Normalizer
				Clustering	MSE	MLPRegressor
Car Price	15	159	Regression	Regression	RMSE	SVR
				Classification	RMSE	RandomForestRegressor
				Clustering	F1-Score	KNeighborsRegressor

Table 17: Recommendation output for the domain expert validation of the LP model. For each dataset, the top three intents, metrics and constraints are provided. The errors identified by the expert are highlighted in bold

4.5 Maintenance and Updates of Knowledge Graph Embeddings

As the Data Abstraction Assistant evolves, the underlying KG must be continuously updated to reflect new users, datasets, algorithms, and workflows. These updates directly affect the KGEs, which provide the vectorized representations used in downstream tasks such as recommendation or intent anticipation. Unlike static KGs, where embeddings can be trained once on a fixed snapshot, dynamic KGs require methods to efficiently incorporate new information while preserving previously learned knowledge. This section addresses the challenges of updating KGEs incrementally, focusing on strategies to mitigate catastrophic forgetting and to ensure that embeddings remain accurate and useful as the KG grows.

4.5.1 Overview

KGs provide a structured way to represent knowledge by modeling entities and their relations as triples [head, relation, tail]. Besides native reasoning and search, KGs can be exploited in downstream tasks such as recommendation [65] or entity classification [66]. Since ML models typically require vector inputs, KG information is represented as low-dimensional vectors known as KGEs.

Figure 37: Conceptual representation of the potential disruption (represented with a shading area) of existing embeddings when the embedding of a new entity with which they appear in a triple is initialized in a distant (left) or close (right) position from the optimal (left)

KGs evolve as new triples are added, introducing new entities or relations and updating existing ones. Consequently, new embeddings must be learned, and existing ones updated. To avoid retraining from scratch, incremental learning techniques have been proposed, ranging from generic fine-tuning to KGE-specific methods like LKGE [67] and incDE [68].

A key step is the initialization of new embeddings. Poor initialization (Figure 37, left) increases training steps and aggravates *catastrophic forgetting*—the loss of previously acquired knowledge. For example, if a new triple [head entity, relation, tail entity] is added, where head is new but relation and tail already appear in many triples, initializing head far from its optimal position can cause large adjustments that degrade the learned representations of relation and tail.

Traditionally, embeddings are randomly initialized, as in training from scratch. However, in incremental learning, existing embeddings can be exploited. We propose a method for initializing new embeddings to accelerate knowledge acquisition while reducing catastrophic forgetting. This is especially relevant in domains with frequent, small updates, such as recommender systems, where each new interaction or item should immediately influence embeddings.

Our approach leverages the KG’s ontology. Ontologies define the schema of classes, relations, and their axioms. Here, new entities are initialized to the centroid of entities in their class. This way, embeddings inherit latent information from class-level representations, acquiring useful knowledge from the start.

Such initialization enables KGEs to adapt to small updates while preserving utility until full retraining. Moreover, since initialization is the first step of incremental learning methods (e.g., regularization, distillation, rehearsal), our approach can improve their predictive performance and efficiency.

4.5.2 Methodology

We present a simple yet effective model-agnostic approach to initialize the embeddings of new entities by exploiting the ontology of the KG. Concretely (see Figure 38), when new triples arrive to the KG containing new entities, an initialization is provided by using existing information (i.e., the already existing embeddings and the ontology). After the initialization, the embeddings can be updated with any KGE incremental learning technique. The goal of the proposed initialization is to reduce catastrophic forgetting by placing the new entities closer to their final positions, thus minimizing excessive changes on existing entities and reducing training time.

Figure 38: Illustration of the overall process for updating KGE with new information

The proposed initialization technique uses the KG's ontology. The ontology defines the schema and structure of a KG, details the entity and relation types, and specifies the rules and constraints which describe how information should be represented and interconnected. For instance (see Figure 39) entities are categorized under a class hierarchy and the relations between them are characterized by domain and range properties.

Figure 39: Example of the ontology information for the triple [J. Phoenix, actedIn, Joker]

Concretely, in the proposed initialization approach, the classes defined in the ontology are used for the initialization of the entities. The idea behind this method is that the entities that share some parts of the ontology (i.e., semantically closer to each other) will be placed near to each other in the embedding space (see Figure 37). Therefore, this method starts by computing the average embedding for each class (i.e., centroid). Then when a new entity is added, its embedding is initialized with the average of the centroids corresponding to the classes that define it. If two new entities share all their classes, they would be initialized with the same exact embeddings, which could be an undesired behaviour [71]. To avoid this, the standard deviation of every class for each dimension of the embedding space is computed. Then, a random factor is added to the entity initialization, which is proportional to the standard deviation of all the classes the entity belongs to. Once the embeddings for new entities are initialized, the KGEs continue to be optimized using the selected incremental learning method.

The initialization is presented in the equation below, where \mathbf{e}_i is the embedding of the new entity i , C_i is the set of classes to which i belongs to, \mathbf{e}_c is the centroid of class c , σ_c is the standard deviation of class c , γ is a factor controlling the random perturbation based on the standard deviations and \mathbf{r} is a random vector sampled independently for every term in the summation.

$$\mathbf{e}_i = \frac{1}{|C_i|} \sum_{c \in C_i} \mathbf{e}_c + \gamma \cdot \frac{1}{|C_i|} \sum_{c \in C_i} \sigma_c \cdot \mathbf{r}_c,$$

Finally, note that this approach can also be applied to relations by using their ontology information (i.e., the hierarchical relationships between them) to initialize them. However, introducing new relations is less common than introducing new entities, as the former typically requires changes in the ontology or schema. For instance, in the KG used for a movie recommender system exemplified in the Overview section, new users, new movies and new interactions are added to the KG constantly, but relations are only added if there is a change in the schema design, which may be significant enough to consider retraining.

4.5.3 Experimental evaluation

This section presents the experiments, which primarily focus on evaluating the benefits of the proposed initialization method on various incremental learning approaches, compared to existing initialization strategies. First, we introduce the initialization and incremental learning techniques, along with the datasets and evaluation metrics. Finally, we present the experimental results.

4.5.3.1 Experimental setting

This work proposes an initialization method capable of mitigating catastrophic forgetting while effectively incorporating new information into existing KGEs. As introduced earlier the focus is on the setting where this information is incrementally introduced in between retraining events and in small updates compared to the original KG size. Here, we describe the datasets that represent such a scenario, along with the metrics to quantify the desired behaviour of the KGE updates. Also, the different initialization methods assessed are briefly described, along with the incremental learning techniques to which they will be applied.

Datasets. The datasets are created from FB15-237 [72], a KG completion dataset based on Freebase. The datasets aim to simulate the incremental addition of new entities to a KG. Therefore, following a similar approach to [67], they consist of an initial set of triples (Snapshot 0), which act as the base KG, and 4 additional sets (Snapshots 1-4) that introduce new entities. Each snapshot is appropriately split into train, validation, and test sets. The training set is used to update the embeddings, the validation set for early stopping and the test set to report the results. The base KG (i.e., Snapshot 0) contains 46000 triples and 2909 entities. In each additional snapshot N new entities are incorporated, and the datasets are named *ENTITY-N*, where N represents the number of new entities in the snapshot. Note that N is not the size of the dataset, but the number of new entities introduced in its triples, as the dataset might also contain triples formed by already existing entities (see Table 18).

	ENTITY-10	ENTITY-50	ENTITY-100	ENTITY-200	ENTITY-500	ENTITY-750	ENTITY-1000
Snapshot 0	27832	27832	27832	27832	27832	27832	27832
Snapshot 1	148	530	1895	3326	8536	13086	17984
Snapshot 2	85	971	1630	3484	9448	14605	19143
Snapshot 3	105	955	1781	3649	9745	13931	18475
Snapshot 4	138	870	1899	3592	9389	13972	18059

Table 18: Number of triples in each snapshot for the different datasets. Snapshot 0 being the base/initial KG.

Metrics. The effect of the initialization will be evaluated with a link prediction (LP) task, as typically done in KGE evaluation. LP aims to predict the missing entity in an incomplete triple (e.g., [head, relation, ?] or [?, relation, tail]) by ranking the plausibility of all the entities in the KG for the missing position. Therefore, usual LP metrics will be used to evaluate the predictive performance, which will be reported by aggregating the results of all the test sets after training with the final snapshot:

- Hits@ k indicates the proportion of incomplete triples in which the correct answer is ranked among the top k positions. The k used in the experiments is 1, 3 and 10.
- Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) measures how early the correct entity is predicted, averaging the inverse of its rank across all incomplete triples.

Furthermore, different metrics from [38] have been adapted to monitor catastrophic forgetting and the acquisition of new knowledge when adding the S additional snapshots. These metrics are derived from the previously defined LP performance metrics, where $\alpha_{i,j}$ represents the value of a given LP evaluation metric on the i -th test dataset after training with the j -th snapshot:

- Ω_{base} has been defined to quantify the retention of old knowledge. It computes the average loss in the evaluation metrics over the base KG every time a new snapshot is added.

$$\Omega_{base} = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{j=1}^S \frac{\alpha_{0,j}}{\alpha_{0,0}}$$

- Ω_{new} has been defined to quantify the acquisition of new knowledge. It is computed as the average predictive performances of the new snapshots when they are introduced.

$$\Omega_{new} = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{i=1}^S \alpha_{i,i}$$

Initialization Strategies. Our proposed initialization approach has been compared to the following initialization techniques:

- **Random Initialization:** This method serves as the baseline and involves initializing the embeddings of new entities randomly. For consistency, this initialization mechanism matches the one used for initializing entities in Snapshot 0, which is the Xavier initialization method.
- **Model Initialization:** As introduced in Section III, some works have proposed to initialize the embeddings with the expected position of its KGE model.

Incremental Learning Strategies. The effect of the initialization has been studied by applying it to different incremental learning approaches. For every method, all the experiments start from the same KGEs obtained for Snapshot 0, thus fixing KGE parameters such as the embedding dimension.

First, and as a baseline, fine-tuning has been explored. This approach involves using only the data from the current snapshot to train the already existing KGEs. Next, generic continual learning approaches that extend fine-tuning have been examined. Specifically, EWC [69] is based on penalizing changes in the embeddings of old parameters, while EMR [70] is a rehearsal-based model that incorporates old samples into the new data to retain prior knowledge. Additionally, the initialization strategies have been applied to methods specifically designed for the incremental learning of KGEs. These include LKGE [67], which uses knowledge transfer techniques to inject knowledge into new entities and applies regularization to avoid catastrophic forgetting, and incDE [68], which defines a learning order for new triples to prioritize the graph structure while using incremental distillation techniques to address knowledge retention. Finally, the results have been compared to a retraining approach, which involves training from scratch at every snapshot using all the available data.

As the model initialization is not compatible with all KGE models and the available implementations of LKGE and incDE are limited to TransE, it has been used as the base KGE model. Nevertheless, we also conducted experiments with other KGE models to demonstrate the model-agnostic improvements of the ontology initialization.

Incremental Learning	Initialization	MRR	Hits@1	Hits@3	Hits@10	Ω_{base}	Ω_{new}
Retraining	–	0.300	0.180	0.351	0.530	–	–
Fine-Tuning	Random	0.175	0.074	0.206	0.366	0.648	0.326
	Model	0.225	0.115	0.260	0.437	0.770	0.329
	Ontology	0.260	0.144	0.303	0.486	0.897	0.388
EWC	Random	0.260	0.146	0.302	0.485	0.912	0.277
	Model	0.264	0.144	0.308	0.497	0.915	0.300
	Ontology	0.276	0.157	0.321	0.507	0.957	0.347
EMR	Random	0.177	0.077	0.208	0.369	0.670	0.303
	Model	0.231	0.121	0.269	0.445	0.803	0.318
	Ontology	0.259	0.142	0.303	0.488	0.899	0.341
LKGE	Random	0.264	0.154	0.302	0.482	0.896	0.281
	Model	0.290	0.170	0.338	0.524	0.944	0.355
	Ontology	0.294	0.177	0.340	0.522	0.966	0.337
incDE	Random	0.288	0.173	0.335	0.509	0.888	0.358
	Model	0.296	0.174	0.350	0.532	0.898	0.370
	Ontology	0.316	0.190	0.375	0.557	0.950	0.405

Table 19: *Effect of different initialization strategies on various incremental learning approaches for ENTITY-100*

4.5.3.2 Initialization Effect on Incremental Learning Approaches

The main experiments have been conducted using the ENTITY-100 dataset. With it, the number of new entities introduced per snapshot is small enough to represent incremental updates, while the cumulative number of new entities added across all additional snapshots results in a 20% increase compared to the initial snapshot. Table 19 shows the results of the different initialization strategies for various incremental learning approaches. The first noteworthy observation is that employing initialization strategies enhances the performance across all metrics compared to relying on random initialization. For instance, let's focus on the Hits@3 when using our proposed ontology initialization. Compared to random initialization, its effect is particularly significant in the simpler approaches, fine-tuning and EMR, with 47% and 45.6% improvements respectively. It also helps enhancing regularized methods, with a 6.2%, 12.5% and 11.9% improvements for EWC, LKGE and incDE, respectively. Significant improvements with respect to random initialization can also be observed for the retention of old knowledge (Ω_{base}), while at the same time increasing the acquisition of new one (Ω_{new}). For instance, in fine-tuning the retention of base knowledge goes from 64.8% in random initialization to 89.7% with ontology initialization, while also increasing the acquisition of new knowledge by a 19%. Therefore, the main drawback of fine-tuning (i.e., catastrophic forgetting) can be mitigated without compromising its updating capabilities. In this context, it can be observed that under these settings, using fine-tuning with a proper initialization is comparable to using a task-specific incremental learning approach, LKGE, with random Initialization. If we compare the initialization strategies, the ontology initialization clearly outperforms the model initialization with all the incremental learning strategies except for LKGE, where a more similar performance is observed.

4.5.3.3 Number of Training Epochs

As exemplified in Figure 37 a more effective initialization of an embedding could reduce the distance to its final values and thus shorten the time required to adjust the embedding during training and minimize the undesired changed of existing embeddings. To evaluate this hypothesis, an experiment has been conducted in which the number of allowed training epochs for the additional snapshots has been limited to different values in the range 10 to 200. The results of the experiments are shown in Figure 40 for Hits@3, Ω_{new} and Ω_{base} , which compare the effect of different initialization strategies for various incremental learning methods. For the acquisition of new knowledge Ω_{new} , the random

initialization is clearly outperformed by the other initializations across all incremental learning approaches. Specifically, not only more new knowledge is obtained but it is also acquired much faster. For instance, the new knowledge obtained with 200 epochs with random initialization is similar to the one obtained with the ontology initialization with 25 epochs, which also has a higher Hits@3 score. When comparing the initialization strategies, the ontology initialization acquires knowledge faster than model initialization, except for the LKGE approach.

However, this increase in Ω_{new} is translated into lower Ω_{base} and Hits@3 results. For the retention of old knowledge Ω_{base} , again, the random initialization is outperformed by the model and ontology initializations, the latter being the one obtaining the best results for all incremental learning approaches. Concretely, the most notable improvements are seen for the non-regularized methods (i.e., fine-tuning and EMR), where the retention of old knowledge is significantly lost as new knowledge is gained.

Finally, for Hits@3, the ontology and model initializations show a more stable behaviour and obtain better results compared to random initialization. Once again, the ontology initialization obtained better results. Therefore, the experiments clearly demonstrate that an effective initialization can reduce the number of epochs (i.e., time) required to incorporate new information into existing KGEs, while also yielding higher evaluation metric scores.

Figure 40: Hits@3, Ω_{new} and Ω_{base} for datasets with different update sizes, when using random, ontology and model initializations

4.5.3.4 Number of New Entities

An additional experiment was conducted to evaluate the effect of the number of new entities added in each snapshot. Specifically, the experiment focuses on assessing to which extent the deviations from our problem setting (i.e., a KG receiving minor incremental updates) still yield significant improvements. Therefore, the datasets used in this experiment add a fixed number of entities in each additional snapshot ranging from 10 to 1000, through the addition of new triples.

In Figure 41, the results of the random, ontology and model initializations are shown. First of all, and as also seen in previous experiments, non-regularized incremental learning approaches (i.e., fine-tuning and EMR) are the ones that benefit the most from a non-random initialization, improving knowledge retention (i.e., Ω_{base}) across all datasets and impacting the overall predictive performance for the ontology initialization.

In general, the benefits can be observed for datasets which add 10-200 new entities in each snapshot. The benefits are particularly significant for Ω_{new} when the number of new entities is small (i.e., +100% for the ontology initialization with ENTITY-10), making a proper initialization an effective strategy in settings where the evaluation metrics for newly added entities are crucial. However, as the number of new entities per snapshot increases beyond the 10-200 range, the improvements compared to the random initialization across the different metrics diminish or disappear. This behaviour can be understood by considering that the newer entities (and thus more triples) introduced in a new snapshot, the more the old embeddings should change and the less this old knowledge should influence the new one. For instance, if we consider the setting where 1000 new entities are introduced in every snapshot (e.g., ENTITY-1000 dataset), the total number of new triples after adding the new triples for all four additional snapshots exceed the original number of triples. Therefore, when handling minor incremental updates, using initialization strategies results in significant improvements, but these benefits diminish as the number of new entities increases.

KGE Type	KGE Model	Hits@3	Ω_{base}	Ω_{new}
Translational	TransH	28.42%	15.48%	19.92%
	TransR	100.40%	56.85%	44.36%
	RotatE	5.38%	4.62%	13.08%
Semantic	DistMult	11.59%	5.12%	48.58%
	SimpleE	28.30%	0.00%	2606.28%
	HolE	26.29%	6.62%	119.63%
Neural Network	ConvE	398.08%	2276.92%	-9.62%
	ProjE	3.40%	-0.11%	42.16%

Table 20: Relative percentage difference between Ontology and Random initialization with various KGE models. Large or >100% values occur when the baseline (Random) is very small; negative values indicate performance degradation.

4.5.3.5 Different KGE Models

For comparability purposes, the previous experiments used TransE as the model to generate the embeddings. This choice was made because the model initialization does not work with every KGE model and because the available implementations of LKGE and incDE only focus on TransE. However, given that the ontology initialization can be easily applied to any KGE model, its usefulness has been tested for different translational, semantic, and neural network based KGE approaches. In Table 20 the results obtained for the fine-tuning setting are shown, where the improvements of the ontology initialization over the random initialization on Hits@3, Ω_{base} and Ω_{new} are presented as percentages. Regarding Hits@3, it can be observed that all the models benefit from the ontology initialization. For

the retention of old knowledge, Ω_{base} is improved in all models except for SimpleE and ProjE. This behaviour is due to the fact that with random initialization these models fail to incorporate new knowledge and just conserve the old one. A similar scenario is seen in Ω_{new} , where with ConvE and random initialization, the model obtains high values of Ω_{new} but rapidly and extensively forgets previous knowledge. With the ontology initialization however, the model does not overfit on new data with ConvE, obtaining significant improvements in Hits@3 and Ω_{base} . Therefore, the different types of KGEs benefit from the ontology initialization, obtaining improvements in the evaluation metrics and in the behaviour of the updating process (e.g., catastrophic forgetting).

Figure 41: Effect of training with reduced number of epochs for different initialization strategies with the ENTITY-100 dataset

5. Gamified simulations for user feedback collection and analysis (T4.5)

The role of the gamification module is to process preselected metadata generated in the ExtremeXP experiments to feed individual and collective challenges and generate virtual or real-life rewards that users can check.

This task includes the design and the development of the gamification module structure, the gamification mechanisms, and the user interfaces.

The following architecture has been defined and implemented:

- A gamification parameter repository to centralize the configurable metadata used in the gamification module.
- A metrics repository to store the user metrics generated during the experiments.

The workflow below has been defined and implemented:

- The gamification module connects to the metrics repository through an API and retrieves the user metrics to feed the gamification engine.
- The gamification engine processes the user metrics according to the rules defined by a Use Case user with manager rights.
- The gamification engine displays the results to the user in the form of forms of virtual rewards/trophies.

T4.5 – Data flow in the gamification module

The task leader (Interactive 4D) and DFKI have selected compatible technologies, among which the game engine Unity 3D and C# programming language, to develop their components so as to ensure a full integration of the gamification module in their Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality platform.

The design and development of the various components of task T4.5 has been structured in three phases.

- **The first phase** corresponds to a core framework designed and developed by the task leader. This core framework is the underlying level upon which the gamification module is developed.
- **The second phase** concerns the development of the gamification engine itself. This gamification engine includes the gamification mechanisms and has been structured along two access levels:
 - A user-level access, displaying virtual rewards and ranking of experiments based on the metrics retrieved from the metrics repository.

Gamification module - User view (panel My rewards)

Gamification module - User view (panel Ranking of my experiments)

- A manager-level access that can define the gamification rules of each use case. These rules are configured with a rewards editor that classifies the metrics retrieved from the metrics repository using thresholds and comparison operators (e.g., Reward X if metric ‘experiment_completion_rate’ ≥ 80%). Virtual rewards are automatically assigned to each user based on the results of this classification.

Gamification module (Manager view)

- **The third phase** corresponds to the development of various user interfaces and their integration in the ExtremeXP framework. These interfaces have been designed and developed as flexible reusable components:

- As a standalone application, in 4 different formats:
 - As a Windows application
 - As a WebGL application, visible within a web browser
 - As an Android mobile application
 - As an iOS mobile application
- As an iframe component integrated in the virtual dashboard developed in Task 4.1 and T4.2

Gamification module (iframe view)

- As an integrated VR component of the virtual dashboard developed by DFKI and visible through a Microsoft HoloLens headset.

Gamification module (Manager view in the VR dashboard)

6. Human-in-the-Loop services for ExtremeXP (Architecture and UI demonstration)

HITL services conveniently integrate into the rest of the ExtremeXP framework (see Figure 42) as an alternative entry point for end users’ access, especially those with lower technical skills. Namely, instead of manually defining experiments and underlying complex analytics workflows (CAW) to be run, end users can access the system via end user interface, through which they can initiate the interaction by expressing their intents in a more human-friendly manner. The HITL services enhance end user experience by learning user profiles from previous user interactions, allowing the anticipation of user intents and thus smoother user experience. Once intent is captured and mapped to the knowledge graph, HITL services then semi-automatically (always keeping the end user in the loop) generate CAWs necessary to satisfy the provided intent. Users can then use the generated CAWs in the Experimentation Engine module (results of WP5) and complete their experimental tasks. Lastly, users can also use provided gamification module to provide feedback on the generated CAWs and the obtained results.

Figure 42: Overview of HITL services in the ExtremeXP framework

Assuming that the ExtremeXP user has previously provided a data product (dataset) via Data Abstraction Layer (DAL) of WP2, they need to specify the analytical intent (e.g., classify, predict, explain, cluster, etc.).

Figure 43: End user’s intent provisioning (left: Expert user intent selection; right: Novice user textual intent expression)

Expert users can automatically select it from a dropdown list (see Figure 43, left), or for novice users, the intent can be automatically detected from the text description of the problem (see Figure 43, right). The latter is performed by using LLMs, as explained in Section 4.1.

Figure 44: Intent definition

Once the user expresses the analytical intent (see Figure 44), the system additionally makes suggestions for constraints on the input parameters. As explained in Section 4.4.3, this can be done by directly leveraging the information stored in the KG via SPARQL queries or by employing KGEs. In the tool, we combine both methods and provide explanations for the generated recommendations.

Figure 45: Intent constraint recommendation

For instance, as seen in Figure 45, the algorithm XGBoost is recommended as the most frequently used algorithm for Classification experiments (SPARQL recommendation) and the algorithm DecisionTree is recommended as it is the Classification algorithm used in similar experiments (KGE recommendation).

With the intent clearly defined and captured, the workflow generation can proceed. For this example, we can assume that the end user was not sure about the recommended algorithm (i.e., XGBoost) and wanted to proceed with a general intent for classification. First, the Abstract Planner (Figure 46) can

be executed to obtain an abstract view of the workflow. The results obtained are depicted in Figure 47.

Figure 46: Logical planner (results of the Abstract planner)

Figure 47: Abstract workflow (SVM)

The plans obtained are higher level workflows that can be visualized, as shown in Figure 47. Before proceeding with the execution, the users have the opportunity to filter out the abstract plans that they are not interested in (e.g., Neural Networks and XGBoost).

Workflow planner

Select the Logical Plans to send to the Workflow Planner:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Decision Tree (4/4)	Individual plans	▼
<input type="checkbox"/> Polynomial Svm (0/4)	Individual plans	▼
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rbf Svm (2/4)	Individual plans	▲
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rbf Svm 0	
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rbf Svm 1	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Rbf Svm 2	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Rbf Svm 3	
<input type="checkbox"/> Sigmoid Svm (0/4)	Individual plans	▼

Figure 48: Workflow planner (results of the Logical planner)

Figure 49: Logical plan (SVM, z-score, mean imputation)

Next, the execution of the Logical Planner proceeds in order to refine the remaining abstract plans and produce more complex execution workflows. Similarly to the Abstract Planner, the produced workflows can also be filtered out (Figure 48) and visualized (Figure 49).

Final workflows

	Individual plans					
Decision Tree	Decision Tree 0		STORE	RDF	KNIME	PROACTIVE
	Decision Tree 1		STORE	RDF	KNIME	PROACTIVE
	Decision Tree 2		STORE	RDF	KNIME	PROACTIVE
	Decision Tree 3		STORE	RDF	KNIME	PROACTIVE
Rbf Svm	Individual plans					
	Rbf Svm 0		STORE	RDF	KNIME	PROACTIVE
	Rbf Svm 1		STORE	RDF	KNIME	PROACTIVE

DOWNLOAD ALL RDF REPRESENTATIONS
DOWNLOAD ALL KNIME REPRESENTATIONS
DOWNLOAD INTENT TO DSL

Figure 50: Final workflows for export and use in Experimentation Engine

Finally, the remaining logical plans can be translated to a format of external ML workflow execution engine (e.g., KNime) or an ExtremeXP engine compatible format (Figure 50).

```

1  package Intrusion_Detection;
2
3  workflow Workflow_0 {
4
5      define task DataLoading;
6      define task Partitioning;
7      define task ModelTrain;
8      define task ModelPredict;
9      define task DataStoring;
10
11
12     START -> DataLoading -> Partitioning -> ModelTrain -> ModelPredict -> DataStoring -> END;
13
14
15     task DataLoading {
16     |     implementation "Intrusion_Detection.data_reader_component";
17     |     }
18
19     task Partitioning {
20     |     implementation "Intrusion_Detection.random_absolute_train_test_split";
21     |     }
22
23     task ModelTrain {
24     |     implementation "Intrusion_Detection.decision_tree_learner";
25     |     }
26
27     task ModelPredict {
28     |     implementation "Intrusion_Detection.decision_tree_learner_predictor";
29     |     }
30
31     task DataStoring {
32     |     implementation "Intrusion_Detection.data_writer_component";
33     |     }
34
35
36     define input data InputData;
37
38     configure data InputData {
39     |     path "./C:/Users/UPC/Documents/datasets/uc2Cyber.parquet"
40     |     }
41 }
42
43 workflow Workflow_1 {
44
45
46     define task DataLoading;
47     define task Partitioning;
48
49

```

Figure 51: XXP (eXtremeXP) file format of the produced workflow

A fragment of the produced file in the latter case is depicted in Figure 51.

7. Conclusion

This deliverable presents the final outcomes of the Human-in-the-loop services of the ExtremeXP platform within WP4. More precisely, tasks T4.3, T4.4, and T4.5. The main achievements of this work are the following modules:

- *User oriented interface and knowledge graph-based module for capturing user intents (**Task 4.3**).*
- *Semi-automated module for mapping user intents into complex analytics workflows (**Task 4.3**).*
- *Module for recommending/anticipating user intents based on the previous users' interaction with the system and created user profiles (**Task 4.4**).*
- *Gamification-based module for user feedback collection (**Task 4.5**).*

These modules are currently integrated within the ExtremeXP platform, more precisely, its User Portal, and with several of its use cases (UC1, UC2, and UC5). Following the delivery of the final research methods and core functionalities, HITL services and modules tools resulted from tasks 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5 will be evaluated against use case requirements of remaining use cases and considered for testing deployments at selected use case sites. The components will continue to evolve, taking into account the results of other technical work packages as well as the evolving requirements and constraints of the use cases.

The software components as well as the backbone knowledge graph of Tasks 4.3 and 4.4 are integrated and available within the open source GitHub repository⁵. The software components of Task 4.5 are available on <https://i4dxdp.eu/game>.

⁵ <https://github.com/dtim-upc/Intents2Workflows>

References

- [1] “Shapes constraint language (SHACL),” W3C, Tech. Rep., Jul. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>
- [2] Sarker, I.H.: Data science and analytics: an overview from data-driven smart computing, decision-making and applications perspective. *SN Computer Science* 2(5)
- [3] Vassiliadis, P., Marcel, P., Rizzi, S.: Beyond roll-up’s and drill-down’s: An intentional analytics model to reinvent olap. *Information Systems* (04 2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2019.03.011>
- [4] Zschech, P., Horn, R., Hörschele, D., Janiesch, C., Heinrich, K.: Intelligent user assistance for automated data mining method selection. *Business & Information Systems Engineering* 62, 227–247 (2020)
- [5] Miller, G.A.: Wordnet: a lexical database for english. *Communications of the ACM* 38(11), 39–41 (1995)
- [6] Johann Faouzi and Olivier Colliot. Classic machine learning methods. arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.11470, 2023.
- [7] Pieter Gijssbers and Joaquin Vanschoren. Designing automl systems: Challenges and guidelines. In *Automated Machine Learning: Fundamentals, Methods, and Challenges*. Springer, 2023.
- [8] H2O.ai. H2o automl documentation. <https://docs.h2o.ai/h2o/latest-stable/h2o-r/docs/reference/h2o.automl.html>, 2024.
- [9] C. Maria Keet, Agnieszka Lawrynowicz, Claudia d’Amato, Alexandros Kalousis, Phong Nguyen, Raul Palma, Robert Stevens, and Melanie Hilario. The data mining optimization ontology. *Journal of Web Semantics*, 32:43–53, 2015.
- [10] Pandas user guide. https://pandas.pydata.org/docs/user_guide/index.html, 2024.
- [11] Abu-Salih, B.: Domain-specific knowledge graphs: A survey. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications* 185, 103076 (2021)
- [12] Achiam, J., Adler, S., Agarwal, S., Ahmad, L., Akkaya, I., Aleman, F.L., Almeida, D., Altenschmidt, J., Altman, S., Anadkat, S., et al.: Gpt-4 technical report. arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.08774 (2023)
- [13] Auer, S., Bizer, C., Kobilarov, G., Lehmann, J., Cyganiak, R., Ives, Z.: Dbpedia: A nucleus for a web of open data. In: *international semantic web conference*. pp. 722–735. Springer (2007)
- [14] Ayoola, T., Tyagi, S., Fisher, J., Christodoulopoulos, C., Pierleoni, A.: Refined: An efficient zero-shot-capable approach to end-to-end entity linking. arXiv preprint arXiv:2207.04108 (2022)
- [15] Baek, J., Aji, A.F., Saffari, A.: Knowledge-augmented language model prompting for zero-shot knowledge graph question answering. arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.04136 (2023)
- [16] Barba, E., Procopio, L., Navigli, R.: Extend: Extractive entity disambiguation. In: *Proceedings of the 60th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*. pp. 2478–2488 (2022)
- [17] Brown, T., Mann, B., Ryder, N., Subbiah, M., Kaplan, J.D., Dhariwal, P., Neelakantan, A., Shyam, P., Sastry, G., Askell, A., et al.: Language models are few-shot learners. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 33, 1877–1901 (2020)
- [18] Cucerzan, S.: Large-scale named entity disambiguation based on wikipedia data. In: *Proceedings of the 2007 joint conference on empirical methods in natural language processing and computational natural language learning (EMNLP-CoNLL)*. pp. 708–716 (2007)
- [19] De Cao, N., Izacard, G., Riedel, S., Petroni, F.: Autoregressive entity retrieval. arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.00904 (2020)
- [20] Ding, Y., Zeng, Q., Weninger, T.: Chatel: Entity linking with chatbots. arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.14858 (2024)
- [21] Gabrilovich, E., Ringgaard, M., Subramanya, A.: Facc1: Freebase annotation of clueweb corpora, version 1 (release date 2013-06-26, format version 1, correction level 0) (06 2013)

- [22] Guha, R.V., Brickley, D., Macbeth, S.: Schema. org: evolution of structured data on the web. *Communications of the ACM* 59(2), 44–51 (2016)
- [23] Heist, N., Hertling, S., Ringler, D., Paulheim, H.: Knowledge graphs on the web-an overview. *Knowledge Graphs for eXplainable Artificial Intelligence* pp. 3–22 (2020)
- [24] Hoffart, J., Seufert, S., Nguyen, D.B., Theobald, M., Weikum, G.: Kore: keyphrase overlap relatedness for entity disambiguation. In: *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management*. pp. 545–554 (2012)
- [25] Hu, L., Liu, Z., Zhao, Z., Hou, L., Nie, L., Li, J.: A survey of knowledge enhanced pre-trained language models. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* (2023)
- [26] Ji, Z., Lee, N., Frieske, R., Yu, T., Su, D., Xu, Y., Ishii, E., Bang, Y.J., Madotto, A., Fung, P.: Survey of hallucination in natural language generation. *ACM Computing Surveys* 55(12), 1–38 (2023)
- [27] Le, P., Titov, I.: Improving entity linking by modeling latent relations between mentions. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.10637* (2018)
- [28] Lewis, P., Perez, E., Piktus, A., Petroni, F., Karpukhin, V., Goyal, N., Kuttler, H., Lewis, M., Yih, W.t., Rocktaschel, T., et al.: Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive nlp tasks. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 33, 9459–9474 (2020)
- [29] Logeswaran, L., Chang, M.W., Lee, K., Toutanova, K., Devlin, J., Lee, H.: Zero-shot entity linking by reading entity descriptions. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.07348* (2019)
- [30] Milne, D., Witten, I.H.: Learning to link with wikipedia. In: *Proceedings of the 17th ACM conference on Information and knowledge management*. pp. 509–518 (2008)
- [31] Onoe, Y., Durrett, G.: Fine-grained entity typing for domain independent entity linking. In: *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. vol. 34, pp. 8576–8583 (2020)
- [32] Pan, S., Luo, L., Wang, Y., Chen, C., Wang, J., Wu, X.: Unifying large language models and knowledge graphs: A roadmap. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* (2024)
- [33] Ratnoff, L., Roth, D., Downey, D., Anderson, M.: Local and global algorithms for disambiguation to wikipedia. In: *Proceedings of the 49th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics: Human language technologies*. pp. 1375–1384 (2011)
- [34] Roder, M., Usbeck, R., Hellmann, S., Gerber, D., Both, A.: N3-a collection of datasets for named entity recognition and disambiguation in the nlp interchange format. In: *LREC*. pp. 3529–3533 (2014)
- [35] Speer, R., Chin, J., Havasi, C.: Conceptnet 5.5: An open multilingual graph of general knowledge. In: *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*. vol. 31 (2017)
- [36] Suchanek, F.M., Kasneci, G., Weikum, G.: Yago: a core of semantic knowledge. In: *Proceedings of the 16th international conference on World Wide Web*. pp. 697–706 (2007)
- [37] Sun, J., Xu, C., Tang, L., Wang, S., Lin, C., Gong, Y., Shum, H.Y., Guo, J.: Think on-graph: Deep and responsible reasoning of large language model with knowledge graph. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.07697* (2023)
- [38] Touvron, H., Martin, L., Stone, K., Albert, P., Almahairi, A., Babaei, Y., Bashlykov, N., Batra, S., Bhargava, P., Bhosale, S., et al.: Llama 2: Open foundation and fine-tuned chat models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.09288* (2023)
- [39] Vrandečić, D., Krotzsch, M.: Wikidata: a free collaborative knowledgebase. *Communications of the ACM* 57(10), 78–85 (2014)
- [40] Wen, Y., Wang, Z., Sun, J.: Mindmap: Knowledge graph prompting sparks graph of thoughts in large language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.09729* (2023)
- [41] Wu, L., Petroni, F., Josifoski, M., Riedel, S., Zettlemoyer, L.: Scalable zero-shot entity linking with dense entity retrieval. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1911.03814* (2019)
- [42] Yang, J., Jin, H., Tang, R., Han, X., Feng, Q., Jiang, H., Zhong, S., Yin, B., Hu, X.: Harnessing the power of llms in practice: A survey on chatgpt and beyond. *ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data* (2023)
- [43] T. T. Le, W. Fu, J. H. Moore, Scaling tree-based automated machine learning to biomedical big data with a feature set selector, *Bioinformatics* 36 (1) (2020) 250–256.

- [44] B. Komer, J. Bergstra, C. Eliasmith, Hyperopt-sklearn, Automated Machine Learning: Methods, Systems, Challenges (2019) 97–111.
- [45] M. Hilario, P. Nguyen, H. Do, A. Woznica, A. Kalousis, Ontology-based meta-mining of knowledge discovery workflows, Meta-learning in computational intelligence (2011) 273–315.
- [46] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, J. Vanderplas, A. Passos, D. Cournapeau, M. Brucher, M. Perrot, E. Duchesnay, Scikit-learn: Machine learning in python, Journal of Machine Learning Research 12 (2011) 2825–2830.
- [47] J. Vanschoren, J. van Rijn, B. Bischl, L. Torgo, Openml: Networked science in machine learning, ACM SIGKDD Explorations Newsletter 15 (2013) 49–60. doi:10.1145/2641190.2641198.
- [48] D. Dua, C. Graff, UCI machine learning repository (2017). URL <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml>
- [49] A. Bordes, N. Usunier, A. Garcia-Duran, J. Weston, O. Yakhnenko, Translating embeddings for modeling multi-relational data 2013 (12 2013).
- [50] J. Feng, Knowledge graph embedding by translating on hyperplanes, 2014.
- [51] Y. Lin, Z. Liu, M. Sun, Y. Liu, X. Zhu, Learning entity and relation embeddings for knowledge graph completion, in: Proceedings of the Twenty-Ninth AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence, AAAI’15, AAAI Press, 2015, p. 2181–2187.
- [52] Z. Sun, Z.-H. Deng, J.-Y. Nie, J. Tang, Rotate: Knowledge graph embedding by relational rotation in complex space, arXiv preprint arXiv:1902.10197 (2019).
- [53] B. Yang, W.-t. Yih, X. He, J. Gao, L. Deng, Embedding entities and relations for learning and inference in knowledge bases, arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6575 (2014).
- [54] T. Trouillon, C. R. Dance, J. Welbl, S. Riedel, E. Gaussier, G. Bouchard, Knowledge graph completion via complex tensor factorization, arXiv preprint arXiv:1702.06879 (2017).
- [55] D. Nguyen, T. Nguyen, D. Q. Nguyen, D. Phung, A novel embedding model for knowledge base completion based on convolutional neural network, 2018, pp. 327–333. doi:10.18653/v1/N18-2053.
- [56] Q. Guo, F. Zhuang, C. Qin, H. Zhu, X. Xie, H. Xiong, Q. He, A survey on knowledge graph-based recommender systems, IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering PP (2020) 1–1. doi:10.1109/TKDE.2020.3028705.
- [57] Y. Deng, Recommender systems based on graph embedding techniques: A comprehensive review (09 2021).
- [58] I. Ferrari, G. Frisoni, P. Italiani, G. Moro, C. Sartori, Comprehensive analysis of knowledge graph embedding techniques benchmarked on link prediction, Electronics 11 (2022) 3866. doi:10.3390/electronics11233866.
- [59] A. Rossi, D. Barbosa, D. Firmani, A. Matinata, P. Merialdo, Knowledge graph embedding for link prediction: A comparative analysis, ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data 15 (2021) 1–49. doi:10.1145/3424672.
- [60] R. Jain, The Art of Computer Systems Performance Analysis: Techniques For Experimental Design, Measurement, Simulation, and Modeling, NY: Wiley, 1991.
- [61] M. Ali, M. Berrendorf, C. T. Hoyt, L. Vermue, S. Sharifzadeh, V. Tresp, J. Lehmann, PyKEEN 1.0: A Python Library for Training and Evaluating Knowledge Graph Embeddings, Journal of Machine Learning Research 22 (82) (2021) 1–6. URL <http://jmlr.org/papers/v22/20-825.html>
- [62] J. Qian, G. Li, K. Atkinson, Y. Yue, Understanding negative sampling in knowledge graph embedding, International Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Applications 12 (2021) 71–81. doi:10.5121/ijaia.2021.12105.
- [63] T. Trouillon, J. Welbl, S. Riedel, E. Gaussier, G. Bouchard, Complex embeddings for simple link prediction, 2016.
- [64] H. Kamigaito, K. Hayashi, Comprehensive analysis of negative sampling in knowledge graph representation learning, in: International Conference on Machine Learning, PMLR, 2022, pp. 10661–10675.

- [65] J.-C. Zhang, A. M. Zain, K.-Q. Zhou, X. Chen, and R.-M. Zhang, “A review of recommender systems based on knowledge graph embedding,” *Expert Systems with Applications*, p. 123876, 2024.
- [66] Q. Wang, Z. Mao, B. Wang, and L. Guo, “Knowledge graph embedding: A survey of approaches and applications,” *IEEE transactions on knowledge and data engineering*, vol. 29, no. 12, pp. 2724–2743, 2017.
- [67] Y. Cui, Y. Wang, Z. Sun, W. Liu, Y. Jiang, K. Han, and W. Hu, “Lifelong embedding learning and transfer for growing knowledge graphs,” in *AAAI*, 2023.
- [68] J. Liu, W. Ke, P. Wang, Z. Shang, J. Gao, G. Li, K. Ji, and Y. Liu, “Towards continual knowledge graph embedding via incremental distillation,” in *AAAI*, 2024.
- [69] J. Kirkpatrick, R. Pascanu, N. Rabinowitz, J. Veness, G. Desjardins, A. A. Rusu, K. Milan, J. Quan, T. Ramalho, A. Grabska-Barwinska et al., “Overcoming catastrophic forgetting in neural networks,” *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, vol. 114, no. 13, pp. 3521–3526, 2017.
- [70] H. Wang, W. Xiong, M. Yu, X. Guo, S. Chang, and W. Y. Wang, “Sentence embedding alignment for lifelong relation extraction,” in *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers)*, J. Burstein, C. Doran, and T. Solorio, Eds. Minneapolis, Minnesota: Association for Computational Linguistics, Jun. 2019, pp. 796–806. [Online]. Available: <https://aclanthology.org/N19-1086>
- [71] J. Feng, M. Huang, M. Wang, M. Zhou, Y. Hao, and X. Zhu, “Knowledge graph embedding by flexible translation,” in *Fifteenth International Conference on the Principles of Knowledge Representation and Reasoning*, 2016.
- [72] K. Toutanova and D. Chen, “Observed versus latent features for knowledge base and text inference,” in *Proceedings of the 3rd workshop on continuous vector space models and their compositionality*, 2015, pp. 57–66.
- [73] A. M. Horst, A. P. Hill, and K. B. Gorman, “allisonhorst/palmerpenguins: v0.1.0.” Zenodo, Jul. 25, 2020. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.3960218. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/3960218>. [Accessed: Sep. 28, 2025]
- [74] O. M. William Wolberg, “Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic).” UCI Machine Learning Repository, 1993. doi: 10.24432/C5DW2B. Available: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/17>. [Accessed: Sep. 28, 2025]